

Development of Various Formulations under Magnetohydrodynamics Framework

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DECLARATION

I, **Avirup Chakraborty (Roll No. 21419PHY029)**, hereby declare that, this report entitled “**Development of Various Formulations under Magnetohydrodynamics Framework**” submitted to Institute of Science, Banaras Hindu University towards partial requirement of Master of Science in Physics. If external data, statements, or results are used in this report, they have always been properly recognised and cited.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the work contained in this project report entitled **Development of Various Formulations under Magnetohydrodynamics Framework**” submitted by **Avirup Chakraborty (Roll No. 21419PHY029)**, to Institute of Science, Banaras Hindu University towards partial requirement of Master of Science in Physics has been carried out by him.

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I want to express my sincere gratitude to my parents for their continuous support and inspiration during this journey. I would like to bestow respects in my mother's feet, who is surely showering her blessings on me from beyond spacetime, without whom all of my accomplishments would be inconceivable to even think of, just like physics would be if there were no mathematical framework for supporting it.

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Avirup Chakraborty

Love is the one thing we're capable of perceiving that transcends dimensions of time and space. Maybe we should trust that, even if we can't understand it. – Interstellar (2014)

.....dedicated to my mother, who is the only love in my life.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 What is Plasma?

Under ordinary circumstances, matter on Earth occurs in the three phases of solid, liquid, and gas. Here, 'ordinary' refers to the circumstances relevant for human life on this planet. This state of affairs does not extrapolate beyond earthly scales: astronomers agree that, ignoring the more speculative nature of dark matter, matter in the Universe consists more than 90% of plasma. Hence, plasma is the ordinary state of matter in the Universe.

Plasma was first identified in laboratory by Sir William Crookes. Crookes presented a lecture on what he called "radiant matter" to the British Association for the Advancement of Science, in Sheffield, on Friday, 22 August, 1879. Systematic studies of plasma began with the research of Irving Langmuir and his colleagues in the 1920s. Langmuir also introduced the term "plasma" as a description of ionized gas in 1928. The word "plasma" comes from the Greek word πλάσμα (plásma), which means something moulded. It was applied for the first time by Tonks and Langmuir, in 1929, to describe the inner region, remote from the boundaries, of a glowing ionized gas produced by electric discharge in a tube, the ionized gas as a whole remaining electrically neutral. [1]¹

Plasma is typically an electrically quasi-neutral medium of unbound positive and negative particles (i.e. the overall charge of a plasma is roughly zero). Although these particles are unbound, they are not "free" in the sense of not experiencing forces. Moving charged particles generate electric currents, and any movement of a charged plasma particle affects and is affected by the fields created by the other charges. In turn, this governs collective behaviour with many degrees of variation. Plasma can be produced by raising the temperature of a substance until a reasonably high fractional ionization is obtained. Under thermodynamic equilibrium conditions, the degree of ionization and the electron temperature is closely related. This relation is given by the Saha equation. Although plasmas in local thermodynamic equilibrium are found in many places in nature, as is the case for many astrophysical plasmas, they are not very common in the laboratory. [2]

1.2 Ideal Plasma & Non Ideal Plasmas.

¹ Citations are marked for reference, please see References section (Page no. 50)

Figure 1: Debye Shielding [13]

An ideal plasma is the one in which Coulomb collisions are negligible, otherwise the plasma is non-ideal. At low density, a low-temperature, partly ionized plasma can be regarded as a mixture of ideal gases of electrons, atoms and ions. The particles travel at thermal velocities, mainly along straight paths, and collide with each other only occasionally. In other words, the free path times prove greater than those of inter particle interaction. With an increase in density, mean distances

between the particles decrease and the particles start spending even more time interacting with each other, that is, in the fields of surrounding particles. Under these conditions, the mean energy of inter particle interaction increases. When this energy becomes comparable with the mean kinetic energy of thermal motion, the plasma becomes non-ideal.

In our entire discussion, we will develop our idea based on ideal plasma. So it is important to note down, what are the characteristics should some system to have to be characterized an ideal plasma, based on which entire formulation has to be done. There are two criteria that a system has to fulfil to be characterized an ideal plasma system, namely: Macroscopic Neutrality & Debye Shielding. [1]

In absence of external disturbances, a plasma has to be macroscopically neutral. This means that under equilibrium conditions with no external forces present, in a volume of the plasma sufficiently large to contain a large number of particles and yet sufficiently small compared to the characteristic lengths for variation of macroscopic parameters such as density and temperature, the net resulting electric charge is zero. In the interior of the plasma the microscopic space charge fields cancel each other and no net space charge exists over a macroscopic region. [1]

To maintain the macroscopic charge neutrality, the thermal energy should balance the electrostatic potential energy ideally. Consider, for example, a plasma with a charged particle number density of 10^{20} m^{-3} and suppose that the electron number density (n_e) in a spherical volume of 10^{-3} m radius (r) were to differ by 1% from the positive ion number density (n_i). Denoting the ion charge by '+e' and the electron charge by '-e', the total n_e charge (q) inside the sphere would be

$$q = -\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 (n_i - n_e) \quad (1) [1]$$

and the electric potential (ϕ) at the surface of the sphere would be

$$\phi = \frac{r^2 e}{3\epsilon_0} (ni - ne) \quad (2) [1]$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space. Plugging numerical values into (2) yields

$\phi = 6 \times 10^3$ volts. Recalling that $1 \text{ eV} = 1.602 \times 10^{-19}$ joule, we find that $kT = 1 \text{ eV}$ when $T = -11,600 \text{ K}$, where k is Boltzmann's constant (1.380×10^{-23} joule/K). Therefore, a plasma temperature of several millions of degree Kelvin would be required to balance the electric potential energy with the average thermal particle energy. Departures from macroscopic electrical neutrality can naturally occur only over distances in which a balance is obtained between the thermal particle energy, which tends to disturb the electrical neutrality, and the electrostatic potential energy resulting from any charge separation, which tends to restore the electrical neutrality. This distance is of the order of a characteristic length parameter of the plasma, called the Debye length. When a plasma is instantaneously disturbed from the equilibrium condition, the resulting internal space charge fields give rise to collective particle motions that tend to restore the original charge neutrality. These collective motions are characterized by a natural frequency of oscillation known as the plasma frequency. Since these collective oscillations are high-frequency oscillations, the ions, because of their heavy mass, are to a certain extent unable to follow the motion of the electrons. The electrons oscillate collectively about the heavy ions; the necessary collective restoring force being provided by the ion-electron coulomb attraction. the angular frequency of this collective electron oscillations, called the (electron) plasma frequency, is given by

$$\omega_{pe} = \left(\frac{ne^2}{m\epsilon_0} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3) [1]$$

Collisions between electrons and neutral particles tend to damp these collective oscillations and gradually diminish their amplitude. If the oscillations are to be only slightly damped, it is necessary that the electron neutral collision frequency (ν_{en}) be smaller than the electron plasma frequency,

$$\nu_{en} < \frac{\omega_{pe}}{2\pi} \quad (4) [1]$$

The next most important characteristic is Debye Shielding. The Debye length is an important physical parameter for the description of a plasma. It provides a measure of the distance over which the influence of the electric field of an individual charged particle (or of a surface at

some nonzero potential) is felt by the other charged particles inside the plasma. The charged particles arrange themselves in such a way as to effectively shield any electrostatic fields within a distance of the order of the Debye length. This shielding of electrostatic fields is a consequence of the collective effects of the plasma particles, and is called Debye Shielding. The Debye length is calculated to be

$$\lambda_D = \frac{\epsilon_0 k T}{n e^2} \quad (5) [1]$$

Any electrostatic fields originated outside a Debye sphere of radius λ_D is effectively screened by the charged particles and do not contribute significantly to the electric field existing at its centre.

Consequently, each charge in the plasma interacts collectively only with the charges that lie inside its Debye sphere, its effect on the other charges being effectively negligible. So consequently the dimension of the system to inherently satisfy the macroscopic charge neutrality has to be much greater than the Debye length. If L is a characteristic dimension of the plasma, a first criterion for the definition of a plasma is therefore

$$L \gg \lambda_D \quad (6) [1]$$

Since the shielding effect is the result of the collective particle behaviour inside a Debye sphere, it is also necessary that the number of electrons inside a Debye sphere be very large. A second criterion for the definition of a plasma is therefore

$$\lambda_D^3 n_e \gg 1 \quad (7) [1]$$

1.3 Occurrence of Astrophysical Plasmas

With the progress made in astrophysics and in theoretical physics during the last century, it was realized that most of the matter in the known universe, with a few exceptions such as the surface of cold planets (the Earth, for example) exists as a plasma. There are various scenarios, under which these plasmas can occur, and therefore there is a need of development of various frameworks, for each of the scenarios. In our solar system, the Sun, is a ball,

Figure 2: Various types of plasmas based on plasma parameters [1]

entirely composed of plasma. The plasma is also present in the interplanetary medium, in the form of solar wind, which is a form of a very less dense plasma, composed of highly energetic particles, coming from the Sun. Earth, too have a layer of very less dense plasma, called the Ionosphere. [3]

Beyond the solar system we find a great variety of natural plasmas in stars, interstellar space, galaxies, intergalactic space, and far beyond to systems quite unknown before the starting of astronomy from space vehicles. There we find a variety of phenomena of great cosmological and astrophysical significance, including interstellar shock waves from remote supernova explosions, rapid variations of x-ray fluxes from neutron stars with densities like that of atomic nuclei, pulsating radio stars or pulsars (which are theoretically pictured as rapidly rotating neutron stars with plasmas emitting synchrotron radiation from the surface), and the plasma phenomena around the remarkable black holes (which are considered to be singular regions of space into which matter has collapsed, possessing such a powerful gravitational field that nothing, whether material objects or even light itself, can escape from them). It is therefore can be inferred that analysing the behaviour of plasma in these wide variety of domain, require various frameworks, that we shall develop. We shall discuss in the following pages magnetohydrodynamical modelling of plasma systems, and derive certain conditions the physical quantities have to obey in order for the particular model to be remain valid. For explanation of behaviour of the plasma in highly dense and low temperature regime, such as that of a neutron star, one need quantum magnetohydrodynamics to explain such a system, in which quantum mechanical effects has to be taken into account (See Chapter 2), for explanation of very high velocity plasma, moving near relativistic speeds, one need the formulation of relativistic magnetohydrodynamics (See Chapter 3); for explanation of movement of plasma near the accretion disk of black holes, one need formulation of magneto hydrodynamics, in curved spacetime, which we call general relativistic magnetohydrodynamics(See Chapter 4); for study of plasmas, originating from processes triggered by nuclear reactions, happening in space, such as a Supernova blast, one need to take into consideration not just the motion of electrons and ions alone, it has to include high energetic neutrino motion as well, as neutrinos are generated in weak nuclear interaction processes. The behaviour of plasma, under dominant weak nuclear interaction is called neutrino magnetohydrodynamics (See Chapter 5). [3]

1.4 Dynamics of Plasma as a Fluid

A plasma consists of a very large number of interacting particles and, hence, it is appropriate to use a statistical approach for its analysis. It is the task of kinetic plasma theory to derive equations describing the collective behaviour of the many charged particles that constitute a plasma by applying the methods of statistical mechanics. [3]

Consider a plasma consisting of electrons and one kind of ion. In the statistical description, the information on the individuality of the particles is lost but the relevant physical information on the plasma as a whole is retained and expressed in terms of time-dependent distribution functions $f_\alpha(r, v, t)$ for the electrons and ions ($\alpha = e, i$). These are defined as the density of the representative points of particles of type α in a six-dimensional phase space formed by the three position coordinates (x, y, z) and the three velocity coordinates (v_x, v_y, v_z). The probable number of particles of type α in the six-dimensional volume element $d^3r d^3v$ centred at (r, v) is then given by $f_\alpha(r, v, t) d^3r d^3v$. The total number of particles,

$N_\alpha = \iint f_\alpha d^3r d^3v$, will be assumed constant. The motion of the swarm of representative points in phase space is described by the total time derivative of the distribution function $f_\alpha(r, v, t)$:

$$\frac{df_\alpha}{dt} = \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial r} \frac{dr}{dt} + \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial v} \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial r} + \frac{q_\alpha}{m_\alpha} (E + v \times B) \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial v} \quad (8) [3]$$

Of course, the interesting part of kinetic theory comes with the introduction of interactions or, rather, collisions between the particles. The variation in time of the distribution functions of both electrons and ions is then found from a kinetic equation, known as the Boltzmann equation:

$$\frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial r} + \frac{q_\alpha}{m_\alpha} (E + v \times B) \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial v} = \left(\frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} \right)_{coll} \quad (9) [3]$$

If the collision is neglected this is called Vlasov equation.

Now, $E(r, t)$ and $B(r, t)$ consist of the contributions of the external fields and of the averaged internal fields originating from the long-range inter-particle interactions. A closed system of equations is now obtained by combining either the Boltzmann equation or the Vlasov equation, determining the distribution functions $f_\alpha(r, v, t)$, with Maxwell's equations, determining the electric and magnetic fields $E(r, t)$ and $B(r, t)$, and the expressions for the

charge and current density source terms $\tau(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and $\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The macroscopic variables are obtained taking expectation values of the moments of the distribution function $f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$:

$$n_\alpha = \int f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3\mathbf{r} d^3\mathbf{v} \quad u_\alpha = \frac{1}{n_\alpha} \int \mathbf{v} f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3\mathbf{r} d^3\mathbf{v}$$

$$\tau_\alpha = \sum q_\alpha n_\alpha \quad \mathbf{j}_\alpha = \sum q_\alpha n_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha \quad (10) [3]$$

A systematic procedure to obtain macroscopic equations, not involving details of velocity space any more, is to expand in a finite number of moments of the Boltzmann equation (8), obtained by first multiplying the expressions with powers of \mathbf{v} and then integrating over velocity space:

$$\int d^3\mathbf{v} \dots, \int d^3\mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} \dots, \int d^3\mathbf{v} v v^2 \dots \Big|_{\text{truncate}} [3]$$

This, in turn, involves the moments of the distribution function itself, like the zeroth moment associated with the particle density n_α and the first moment associated with the average velocity $\langle \mathbf{v} \rangle_\alpha \equiv \mathbf{u}_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t)$, just defined. In general, macroscopic variables $\langle g \rangle_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t)$ will appear as the average of some phase space function $g(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ over velocity space:

$\langle g \rangle_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \frac{1}{n_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t)} \int g(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t) f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t) d^3\mathbf{v}$. The zeroth moment of Eq. (9), obtained by integrating over velocity space, yields the following terms: [3]

$$\int \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} d^3\mathbf{v} = \frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial t}$$

$$\int \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{r}} d^3\mathbf{v} = \nabla \cdot (n_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha) [3]$$

$$\int \frac{q_\alpha}{m_\alpha} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot \frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{v}} d^3\mathbf{v} = 0$$

$$\int C_\alpha d^3\mathbf{v} = 0$$

In the same vein, the first moment of Eq. (9), obtained by multiplying with $m_\alpha \mathbf{v}$ and integrating over the velocities, yields the momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (n_\alpha m_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha) + \nabla \cdot (n_\alpha m_\alpha \langle \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} \rangle_\alpha) - q_\alpha n_\alpha (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_\alpha \times \mathbf{B}) = \int C_{\alpha\beta} m_\alpha \mathbf{v} d^3\mathbf{v}$$

Finally, the scalar second moment of Eq. (9), obtained by multiplying with $\frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2$ and integrating over velocity space, yields the energy equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(n_\alpha \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha \langle v^2 \rangle_\alpha \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(n_\alpha \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha \langle v^2 \mathbf{v} \rangle_\alpha \right) - q_\alpha n_\alpha \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\alpha = \int C_{\alpha\beta} \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2 d^3\mathbf{v}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) &\equiv \frac{m_\alpha}{3k} \langle \tilde{v}_\alpha^2 \rangle \\
\mathbf{P}_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) &\equiv n_\alpha m_\alpha \langle \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_\alpha \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_\alpha \rangle = p_\alpha \mathbf{I} + \pi_\alpha, \\
p_\alpha &\equiv n_\alpha k T_\alpha \\
\text{Defining the quantities } \mathbf{h}_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) &\equiv \frac{1}{2} n_\alpha m_\alpha \langle \tilde{v}_\alpha^2 \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_\alpha \rangle \quad [3] \\
\mathbf{R}_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) &\equiv m_\alpha \int C_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_\alpha d^3v \\
Q_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) &\equiv \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha \int C_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{v}_\alpha^2 d^3v
\end{aligned}$$

We now use the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and cancel the collision terms in (9) we get the equations of continuity, momentum, and heat balance (energy conservation)

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha) &= 0, \\
n_\alpha m_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_\alpha \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_\alpha \right) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_\alpha - n_\alpha q_\alpha (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_\alpha \times \mathbf{B}) &= \mathbf{R}_\alpha \quad [3] \\
\frac{3}{2} n_\alpha k \left(\frac{\partial T_\alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_\alpha \cdot \nabla T_\alpha \right) + \mathbf{P}_\alpha : \nabla \mathbf{u}_\alpha + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{h}_\alpha &= Q_\alpha.
\end{aligned}$$

Considering electrons and ions as two non-interacting fluids, the two fluid model system of equations are written as

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_e \cdot \nabla \right) n_e + n_e \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_e &= 0, \\
\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \nabla \right) n_i + n_i \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_i &= 0, \\
n_e m_e \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_e \cdot \nabla \right) \mathbf{u}_e + \nabla p_e + e n_e (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}) &= -\nabla \cdot \pi_e + \mathbf{R}_e, \\
n_i m_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \nabla \right) \mathbf{u}_i + \nabla p_i - Z e n_i (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_i \times \mathbf{B}) &= -\nabla \cdot \pi_i - \mathbf{R}_e, \quad [3] \\
\frac{3}{2} n_e \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_e \cdot \nabla \right) k T_e + p_e \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_e &= -\pi_e : \nabla \mathbf{u}_e - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{h}_e - (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \mathbf{R}_e - Q_i, \\
\frac{3}{2} n_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \nabla \right) k T_i + p_i \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_i &= -\pi_i : \nabla \mathbf{u}_i - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{h}_i + Q_i,
\end{aligned}$$

For the fluid model we assume that the plasma follows the equations of gas dynamics,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &\equiv \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \\
\frac{Dp}{Dt} + \gamma p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &\equiv \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla p + \gamma p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad [3]
\end{aligned}$$

Here, $\frac{D}{Dt} \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla$ is the Lagrangian time derivative, which is the time derivative evaluated while moving with the fluid. As well the Maxwell's equations

$$\begin{aligned}
\nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\
\nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \mathbf{j} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \\
\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= \frac{\tau}{\epsilon_0} \\
\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Next, one of the most characteristic equations describing the plasma state is the equation for the electric field in a perfectly conducting moving fluid, expressing the electric vanishes in the commoving frame.

$$\mathbf{E}' \equiv \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad [3]$$

The fluid equations then can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) &= 0, \\
\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} \right) + \nabla p - \rho \mathbf{g} - \frac{1}{\mu_0} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla p + \gamma p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) &= 0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

The conservation form of the above equations can be derived by evaluating $\left(\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} \right) + \nabla p - \rho \mathbf{g} - \frac{1}{\mu_0} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} = 0 \right) \times \mathbf{v}$ & $\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \right) \times \mathbf{B}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \left[\rho \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} + \left(p + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \right) \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B} \right] &= -\rho \nabla \Phi, \\
p &= (\gamma - 1) \rho e, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho e + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho e + p + B^2 \right) \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B} \right] & \\
\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v} \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{B} \mathbf{v}) &= 0, \nabla \cdot -\nabla \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \Phi,
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The last few pages captures the essence of the fundamental fluid model we are about to put to use in the following pages.

Figure 3: Magnetic stress and tension in MHD fluid [3]

Chapter 2: Quantum Magnetohydrodynamics

2.1 What are Quantum Plasmas?

As we have already defined what a plasma is in previous chapter we are now in a good position to develop a framework for the explanation of plasma under quantum mechanical regime. But in order to do so, let us first discuss what are the most significant parameters the macroscopic behaviour of the plasma is dependent upon. It has been established that there are two basic parameters namely temperature and number density of particles, which determine the behaviour of plasma.

The absolute temperature T_α , for the type α particles, is a measure of the mean kinetic energy of the random particle motions. According to the thermodynamic definition of absolute temperature, there is a mean thermal energy of $kT_{\alpha i}/2$ associated with each translational degree of freedom ($i = x, y, z$), so that

$$\frac{1}{2}kT_{\alpha i} = \frac{1}{2}m_\alpha \langle c_{\alpha i}^2 \rangle \quad (11) [1]$$

To associate a meaning to the expression “small temperature,” it is necessary to compare the thermal and interaction energies of the system. In this way, a coupling parameter can be defined, as the ratio between thermal and binding energies. Indeed, in the transformation from plasma to neutral gas, and then to liquid, and then to solid, the particles of the system became more and more attached specially due to the organizing character of the Coulomb force. Hence, in our definition of a plasma, we can add the requirement of a sufficiently high thermal energy, in comparison to the binding energy. [3]

Besides temperature, the density (number of particles per unit volume) is a fundamental parameter of a plasma. In a first guess, we would imagine that extremely dense plasmas should be necessarily strongly coupled. This would be the case, for instance, for the plasma in massive compact astrophysical objects like white dwarfs, where the density is as high as 10^{36} m^{-3} . However, this is not the case due to the Pauli exclusion principle, which significantly inhibit collisions. Extremely dense plasmas behave in an even more ideal way as the density increases because the occupation of the same quantum state by two spin 1/2 fermions is forbidden. [4]

When are quantum effects relevant for plasmas? Extremely dense plasmas behave like a quantum ideal gas, due to the exclusion principle. However, also dilute charged particle systems can exhibit quantum features, provided the dimensions of the system are small enough. Small enough here means dimensions comparable to the de Broglie wavelength

$\lambda_B = \frac{h}{mv_T}$, where $v_T = \left(\frac{\kappa_B T}{m}\right)^{1/2}$ is the thermal velocity. Hence, if L_0 is a typical length scale of the plasma, quantum effects should be taken into account whenever $\lambda_D \sim L_0$. The Maxwell Boltzmann probability distribution describing the dilute plasma, then has to be replaced by the Fermi Dirac distribution function, which obeys the Pauli exclusion principle. An intuitive approach to this problem would assume a homogeneous one-particle probability distribution function in a sphere of radius v_F in velocity space, where v_F is the Fermi velocity. Therefore,

$$f = \frac{3n_0}{4\pi v_F^3} \quad \text{if } \frac{mv^2}{2} - e\phi < E_F \quad (12) [4]$$

Figure 4: Fermi-Dirac Distribution

& $f = 0$ otherwise. E_F is the Fermi energy, energy of the uppermost occupied energy level as temperature reaches absolute zero. With this statistic the quantum version of Poisson equation for plasma becomes

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{3n_0 e^2}{2\varepsilon_0 E_F} \phi - \frac{qt}{\varepsilon_0} \delta(\mathbf{r}). \quad (13)$$

Correspondingly, the quantum screening distance, or Thomas–Fermi length λ_F , can be defined as $\lambda_F = \left(\frac{2\varepsilon_0 E_F}{3n_0 e^2}\right)^{1/2}$. The corresponding plasma frequency for the quantum case is found to be $\omega_p \lambda_F = \left(\frac{2E_F}{3m}\right)^{1/2} = v_F/\sqrt{3}$. [4]

2.2 Wigner Poisson System Formulation for Quantum Plasma

To maintain the closest resemblance to the familiar methods of classical plasma physics, the Wigner function approach is the natural choice. Indeed, using the Wigner function, one can proceed in almost total analogy with the standard phase space distribution function method to compute macroscopic quantities like number and current densities. Hence, it is useful to

review some of the properties of the Wigner (pseudo) distribution function approach. In addition, the differences between classical and quantum formalisms will be highlighted. It is a quasi-probability distribution. It was introduced by Eugene Wigner in 1932 to study quantum corrections to classical statistical mechanics. The goal was to link the wave function that appears in Schrödinger's equation to a probability distribution in phase space. It is a generating function for all spatial autocorrelation functions of a given quantum-mechanical wave function $\psi(x)$. Thus, it maps on the quantum density matrix in the map between real phase-space functions.

For simplicity, let us start with a one-dimensional, one-particle pure state quantum system, represented by a wave function $\psi(x,t)$. In this case, the Wigner function $f = f(x,v,t)$

$$f = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar} \int ds \exp\left(\frac{imvs}{\hbar}\right) \psi^*\left(x + \frac{s}{2}, t\right) \psi\left(x - \frac{s}{2}, t\right), \quad (14) [4]$$

where x is the position, v the velocity, t the time, m the particle's mass and $\hbar = h/(2\pi)$, where h is Planck's constant. The Wigner function provides a phase-space description of the quantum system, where all physical quantities can be found from the k th-order moments $\int dv v^k f(x,v,t)$. For instance, both the probability density

$$n(x,t) = |\psi(x,t)|^2 = \int dv v f(x,v,t) \quad (15)$$

and the probability current

$$J(x,t) = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \left(\psi \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial x} - \psi^* \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \right) = \int dv v^2 f(x,v,t) \quad (16) [4]$$

can be readily obtained, respectively, from the zeroth and first order moments of the Wigner function. Note the wave function is normalized to unity at all instances. For a one particle quantum mixed state, in which each state is labelled by α , represented by a quantum statistical mixture $\{\psi_\alpha(x,t), p_\alpha\}$, $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, M$, where each wave function $\psi_\alpha(x,t)$ occurs with a probability p_α such that $p_\alpha \geq 0$, $\sum p_\alpha = 1$. In such a situation, the Wigner function is given by the superposition

$$f = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha \int ds \exp\left(\frac{imvs}{\hbar}\right) \psi_\alpha^*\left(x + \frac{s}{2}, t\right) \psi_\alpha\left(x - \frac{s}{2}, t\right) \quad (17) [4]$$

The corresponding zeroth and first order moments of the Wigner function will be

$$n(x,t) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha |\psi_\alpha(x,t)|^2 = \int dv v f(x,v,t), \quad (18)$$

$$J(x, t) = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \left(\psi_{\alpha} \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}^*}{\partial x} - \psi_{\alpha}^* \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}}{\partial x} \right) = \int dv v f(x, v, t). \quad (19) [4]$$

Going one step further, consider now a N-particle statistical mixture described by the set $\{\psi_{\alpha}^N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N, t), p_{\alpha}\}$, where the normalized N-particle ensemble wave functions $\psi_{\alpha}^N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N, t)$ are distributed with probabilities $p_{\alpha}, \alpha = 1, 2, \dots, M$ satisfying $p_{\alpha} \geq 0, \sum p_{\alpha} = 1$ as before. Here, x_i represents the position of the i th particle, $i=1, 2, \dots, N$. For simplicity, assume all particles to have the same mass m . In analogy with (17) the N-particle Wigner function is then defined as

$$\begin{aligned} f^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) &= N \left(\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar} \right)^N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \int ds_1, \dots, ds_N \exp \left(\frac{im \sum_{i=1}^N v_i s_i}{\hbar} \right) \\ &\times \psi_{\alpha}^{N*} \left(x_1 + \frac{s_1}{2}, \dots, x_N + \frac{s_N}{2}, t \right) \\ &\times \psi_{\alpha}^N \left(x_1 - \frac{s_1}{2}, \dots, x_N - \frac{s_N}{2}, t \right). \end{aligned} \quad (20) [4]$$

Next, we have to find the quantum analog of the classical operators in phase space. suppose a classical phase-space function $A(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t)$

corresponding to a self-adjoint quantum mechanical operator $\hat{A}(\hat{x}_1, \hat{v}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_N, \hat{v}_N, t)$. Indeed, to calculate expectation values using the Wigner formalism, we need first to map the observable into a phase-space function using the Weyl correspondence. In practice, this is equivalent to ordering operators into a symmetric product of the position and momenta operators, using the commutation relations and then making the replacements $\hat{x}_i \rightarrow x_i$ and $\hat{p}_i \rightarrow p_i$, where \hat{x}_i, \hat{p}_i are the position and momentum operators of the i th-particle and x_i, p_i the corresponding classical position and momentum functions. Given a classical function $A(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t)$ the phase-space average is $\langle A \rangle_{cl}$ is

$$\langle A \rangle_{cl} = \frac{1}{N} \int dx_1 dv_1, \dots, dx_N dv_N f_{cl}^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) A(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t), \quad (21) [4]$$

while the expectation value \hat{A} of the associated Weyl ordered self-adjoint operator $\hat{A}(\hat{x}_1, \hat{v}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_N, \hat{v}_N, t)$ is:

$$\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \int dx_1 dv_1, \dots, dx_N dv_N f^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) A(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) \quad (22)$$

As already remarked, to obtain non erroneous expectation values of operators involving non commuting observables using the Wigner formalism, the Weyl ordering should be employed. To see an illustrative example, consider the operator

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{x}_i \hat{p}_j &= \frac{1}{2}(\hat{x}_i \hat{p}_j + \hat{p}_j \hat{x}_i) + \frac{1}{2}[\hat{x}_i, \hat{p}_j] \\
&= \frac{1}{2}(\hat{x}_i \hat{p}_j + \hat{p}_j \hat{x}_i) + \frac{i\hbar \delta_{ij}}{2} \quad (23) [4] \\
&\rightarrow x_i p_j + \frac{i\hbar \delta_{ij}}{2} \text{ (Weyl rule)},
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the required expectation value is

$$\langle \hat{x}_i \hat{p}_j \rangle = \frac{m}{N} \int dx_1 dv_1, \dots, dx_N dv_N f^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) x_i v_j + \frac{i\hbar \delta_{ij}}{2} \quad (24) [4]$$

Doing integrations by parts of the right-hand side of (24) we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{m}{N} \int dx_1 dv_1, \dots, dx_N dv_N f^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t) x_i v_j + \frac{i\hbar \delta_{ij}}{2} \\
&= -i\hbar \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \int dx_1, \dots, dx_N \psi_{\alpha}^{N*}(x_1, \dots, x_N, t) x_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \psi_{\alpha}^N(x_1, \dots, x_N, t) \quad (25) [4]
\end{aligned}$$

Now we are in a position to derive the equations of dynamics of the quantum plasma. The Schrödinger's equation determines the time evolution of the quantum system, which for a N body ensemble wave functions can be written as

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}^N}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\alpha}^N}{\partial x_i^2} + V(x_1, \dots, x_N) \psi_{\alpha}^N \quad (26)$$

Multiplying with complex conjugate ψ_{α}^{N*} to both sides of (26), and using definition of the f given in (20), one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{\partial f^N}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N v_i \frac{\partial f^N}{\partial x_i} \\
&= -\frac{i}{\hbar} \left(\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar} \right)^N \int ds_1, \dots, ds_N \exp \left(-\frac{im \sum_{i=1}^N (v'_i - v_i) s_i}{\hbar} \right) (V(\mathbf{x}_+) - V(\mathbf{x}_-)) \quad (27)
\end{aligned}$$

Where we have integrated by parts of the R.H.S. of (26), and have used the relations

$$\begin{aligned}
&\psi_{\alpha}^{N*}(\mathbf{x}_+, t) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\alpha}^N(\mathbf{x}_-, t)}{\partial x_i^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\alpha}^{N*}(\mathbf{x}_+, t)}{\partial x_i^2} \psi_{\alpha}^N(\mathbf{x}_-, t) \\
&= -2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial s_i} [\psi_{\alpha}^{N*}(\mathbf{x}_+, t) \psi_{\alpha}^N(\mathbf{x}_-, t)] \quad [4] \\
&= N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \psi_{\alpha}^{N*}(\mathbf{x}_+, t) \psi_{\alpha}^N(\mathbf{x}_-, t) \\
&= \int dv_1, \dots, dv_N \exp \left(-\frac{im \sum_{i=1}^N v_i s_i}{\hbar} \right) f^N(x_1, v_1, \dots, x_N, v_N, t).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus by the property of the Wigner function, we can see that we can derive the quantum analog of the Vlasov equations, and have condensed all the necessary information about the system in the Wigner functions, where by moment integration, we can derive the macroscopic quantities. However, the Wigner Poisson system is too crude to be put into good use when it comes to calculation of macroscopic quantities as we have to perform rigorous integrations that we have encountered. So it is more advisable to deal with the Poisson

Schrödinger system, where we can make calculations much easily, analogous to the classical system. For the analytical study, the hydrodynamic formulation of the Schrödinger–Poisson system is particularly convenient, since it makes direct use of macroscopic plasma quantities, such as density and average velocity. Moreover, it enables one to perform straightforward perturbation calculations in the same fashion as in the classical case. Hence, let us introduce the amplitude $A_\alpha = A_\alpha(x, t)$ and the phase $S_\alpha = S_\alpha(x, t)$ associated with the pure state $\psi_\alpha = \psi_\alpha(x, t)$ according to $\psi_\alpha = A_\alpha \exp(iS_\alpha/\hbar)$. Both A_α and S_α are defined as real quantities. The density n_α and the velocity u_α of the α th stream of the plasma are given by [4]

$$n_\alpha = A_\alpha^2, u_\alpha = \frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial x} \quad (28) [4]$$

Substituting the wave function ψ_α in the Schrödinger equation, and separating the real and the complex part one can write using the definition of (28)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(n_\alpha u_\alpha) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial t} + u_\alpha \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial^2(\sqrt{n_\alpha})/\partial x^2}{\sqrt{n_\alpha}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

These are now the new continuity and the momentum conservation equations of N stream quantum plasma. Now we can classical like fluid equations of plasma, in which we can separate the classical and quantum pressure parts, and have a clear understanding how the quantum pressure originates, and under what conditions, it is dominant and significant.

Introducing the standard definitions of density, mean velocity and pressure,

$$n(x, t) = \int f dv, u(x, t) = \frac{1}{n} \int f v dv, P(x, t) = m \left(\int f v^2 dv - nu^2 \right) \quad (30) [4]$$

If we take the zeroth and first moments of the Wigner Poisson system equation (27), and using the definition of (30), we can write the zeroth and first order moment equations as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(nu)}{\partial x} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{mn} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \quad (31) [4]$$

Where we find after delta function integrations, the macroscopic quantities in terms of ensemble wave functions as

$$\begin{aligned} n &= N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha |\psi_\alpha|^2 \\ nu &= \frac{i\hbar N}{2m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha \left(\psi_\alpha \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha^*}{\partial x} - \psi_\alpha^* \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} [4]$$

$$P = \frac{N\hbar^2}{4m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \left(2 \left| \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}}{\partial x} \right|^2 - \psi_{\alpha}^* \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\alpha}}{\partial x^2} - \psi_{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\alpha}^*}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{N^2 \hbar^2}{4mn} \left[\sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \left(\psi_{\alpha}^* \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}}{\partial x} - \psi_{\alpha} \frac{\partial \psi_{\alpha}^*}{\partial x} \right) \right]^2 \quad (32) [4]$$

If we represent each state according to the Madelung decomposition ($\psi_{\alpha} = A_{\alpha} \exp\left(\frac{iS_{\alpha}}{\hbar}\right)$), we shall rewrite (32) in terms of phase and amplitude of wave function ensemble, as:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} A_{\alpha}^2 \\ nu &= \frac{N}{m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} A_{\alpha}^2 \frac{\partial S_{\alpha}}{\partial x} \\ P &= \frac{N^2}{2mn} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^M p_{\alpha} p_{\beta} A_{\alpha}^2 A_{\beta}^2 \left(\frac{\partial S_{\alpha}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial S_{\beta}}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \frac{N\hbar^2}{2m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_{\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{\partial A_{\alpha}}{\partial x} \right)^2 - A_{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 A_{\alpha}}{\partial x^2} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

it is useful to define the kinetic u_{α} and osmotic u_{α}^0 velocities associated with the wave

$$\text{function } \psi_{\alpha}, u_{\alpha} = \frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial S_{\alpha}}{\partial x}, u_{\alpha}^0 = \frac{\hbar}{m} \frac{\partial A_{\alpha} / \partial x}{A_{\alpha}} [4]$$

so that we can write the pressure as

$$\begin{aligned} P &= P^k + P^0 + P^Q \\ P^k &= \frac{mn}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^M \tilde{p}_{\alpha} \tilde{p}_{\beta} (u_{\alpha} - u_{\beta})^2 \\ P^0 &= \frac{mn}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^M \tilde{p}_{\alpha} \tilde{p}_{\beta} (u_{\alpha}^0 - u_{\beta}^0)^2 \\ P^Q &= -\frac{\hbar^2 n}{4m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \ln n \end{aligned} \quad (34) [4]$$

where the P^k , P^0 & P^Q are the kinetic, osmotic and quantum pressure terms. Now if we approximate the solution wave function as a plane wave, $\psi_{\alpha}(x, t) = A_0 \exp\left(\frac{im u_{\alpha} x}{\hbar}\right)$, we can rewrite the momentum conservation and the mass conservation equations (31) as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(nu)}{\partial x} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= -\frac{1}{mn} \frac{\partial P^C(n)}{\partial x} + \frac{e}{m} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial^2(\sqrt{n})/\partial x^2}{\sqrt{n}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (35) [4]$$

Where $P_c = P^k + P^0$. These are the generalized quantum plasma continuity equations, which we now shall use in our derivation of quantum magnetohydrodynamics equations.

$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial^2(\sqrt{n})/\partial x^2}{\sqrt{n}} \right)$ is recognized to be the quantum pressure, which originates because of the divergence in the number density n , thus indicating quantum effects are thus born of the number density gradient of the plasma. [4]

2.3 Quantum Magnetohydrodynamics Equations

Now we shall derive the plasma fluid equations for a Schrödinger Poisson system, by considering the electromagnetic interaction between plasma streams. And then we shall find again by the Madelung decomposition, the quantum pressure part. We begin again by the Schrödinger equation, which under EM Interaction will now be

$$\frac{1}{2m} (-i\hbar\nabla - q\mathbf{A})^2 \psi_\alpha + q\phi\psi_\alpha = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial t} \quad (36) [4]$$

Here, we consider charge carriers of mass m and charge q , subjected to mean field self-consistent scalar and vector potentials $\phi = \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, respectively.

For definiteness, the Coulomb gauge $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$ is chosen. Again multiplying (36) with the complex conjugate, and using the following identities:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int d\mathbf{s} e^{\frac{i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \psi_\alpha^* \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \mathbf{A} \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \cdot \nabla \psi_\alpha \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \\ & + \int d\mathbf{s} e^{\frac{i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \mathbf{A} \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \cdot \nabla \psi_\alpha^* \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \psi_\alpha \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \\ & = \frac{i\mathbf{p}}{\hbar} \cdot \int d\mathbf{s} e^{\frac{i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \left(\mathbf{A} \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) - \mathbf{A} \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \right) \psi_\alpha^* \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \psi_\alpha \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{s}} \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) &= -\frac{1}{2} \nabla \psi_\alpha \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \\ \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha^*}{\partial \mathbf{s}} \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) &= \frac{1}{2} \nabla \psi_\alpha^* \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\int d\mathbf{p} f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}, t) e^{-\frac{i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} = N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha \psi_\alpha^* \left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) \psi_\alpha \left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t \right) [4]$$

We can rewrite (27) for the electromagnetic interaction case as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \frac{\mathbf{p}}{m} \cdot \nabla f \\
&= \frac{iq}{\hbar(2\pi\hbar)^3} \iint ds d\mathbf{p}' e^{\frac{i(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{p}')\cdot\mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \left[\phi\left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) - \phi\left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) \right] f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}', t) \\
&+ \frac{iq^2}{2\hbar m(2\pi\hbar)^3} \iint ds d\mathbf{p}' e^{\frac{i(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{p}')\cdot\mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \left[A^2\left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) - A^2\left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) \right] f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}', t) \quad (37) [4] \\
&+ \frac{q}{2m(2\pi\hbar)^3} \nabla \cdot \iint ds d\mathbf{p}' e^{\frac{i(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{p}')\cdot\mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \left[\mathbf{A}\left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) + \mathbf{A}\left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) \right] f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}', t) \\
&- \frac{iq}{\hbar m(2\pi\hbar)^3} \mathbf{p} \cdot \iint d\mathbf{p}' e^{\frac{i(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{p}')\cdot\mathbf{s}}{\hbar}} \left[\mathbf{A}\left(\mathbf{r} + \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) - \mathbf{A}\left(\mathbf{r} - \frac{\mathbf{s}}{2}, t\right) \right] f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}', t).
\end{aligned}$$

Now again introducing the required moments of the Wigner function in this case, for the derivation of the macroscopic quantities,

$$\begin{aligned}
n &= \int dp f \\
\mathbf{u} &= \frac{1}{mn} \int d\mathbf{p} (\mathbf{p} - q\mathbf{A}) f \\
\mathbf{P} &= \frac{1}{m} \int d\mathbf{p} (\mathbf{p} - q\mathbf{A}) \otimes (\mathbf{p} - q\mathbf{A}) f - mn\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}. [4]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we can write (31) as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n\mathbf{u}) = 0 \\
& \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{mn} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{P} + \frac{q}{m} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (38) [4]
\end{aligned}$$

where we have used the relation $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi - \partial\mathbf{A}/\partial t$ and $\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$. Now doing the Madelung decomposition $\psi_\alpha = A_\alpha \exp(iS_\alpha/\hbar)$, we get the macroscopic quantities as

$$\begin{aligned}
n &= N \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha n_\alpha, \\
\mathbf{u} &= \frac{N}{mn} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha n_\alpha \nabla S_\alpha - \frac{q}{m} \mathbf{A}, \\
\mathbf{P} &= \frac{N}{m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha n_\alpha \nabla S_\alpha \otimes \nabla S_\alpha - \frac{N^2}{mn} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^M p_\alpha p_\beta n_\alpha n_\beta \nabla S_\alpha \otimes \nabla S_\beta \quad (39) [4] \\
&+ \frac{\hbar^2 N}{4m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha \frac{\nabla n_\alpha \otimes \nabla n_\alpha}{n_\alpha} - \frac{\hbar^2 N}{4m} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M p_\alpha \nabla \otimes \nabla n_\alpha.
\end{aligned}$$

Defining again the kinetic velocities and the osmotic velocities as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{u}_\alpha &= \frac{1}{m} [\nabla S_\alpha - q\mathbf{A}], \alpha = 1, \dots, M \\
\mathbf{u}_\alpha^o &= \frac{\hbar}{2m} \frac{\nabla n_\alpha}{n_\alpha}, \alpha = 1, \dots, M [4]
\end{aligned}$$

We can rewrite P in (39) as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{P} &= \frac{mn}{2} \sum_{\alpha,\beta=1}^M \tilde{p}_\alpha \tilde{p}_\beta \left[(\mathbf{u}_\alpha - \mathbf{u}_\beta) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_\alpha - \mathbf{u}_\beta) + (\mathbf{u}_\alpha^o - \mathbf{u}_\beta^o) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_\alpha^o - \mathbf{u}_\beta^o) \right] \\
&- \frac{\hbar^2 n}{4m} \nabla \otimes \nabla \ln n, \quad (40) [4]
\end{aligned}$$

where the quantum pressure is found to be $\frac{\hbar^2 n}{4m} \nabla \otimes \nabla \ln n$. Again doing the plane wave approximation, $\psi_\alpha(x, t) = A_0 \exp\left(\frac{im\mathbf{u}_\alpha x}{\hbar}\right)$, we get the momentum and mass conservation as

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n\mathbf{u}) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{mn} \nabla P^C(n) + \frac{q}{m} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{n}}{\sqrt{n}} \right) \quad (41) [4]$$

Where P_c is nothing but the classical part of the P in (40). Therefore, the equations of the Quantum Magnetohydrodynamics are found to be for electrons and ions as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_e \mathbf{u}_e) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial n_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_i \mathbf{u}_i) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_e}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_e \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_e &= -\frac{\nabla P_e}{m_e n_e} - \frac{e}{m_e} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}) \\ &+ \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^2} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{n_e}}{\sqrt{n_e}} \right) - v_{ei} (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i) \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_i &= -\frac{\nabla P_i}{m_i n_i} + \frac{e}{m_i} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_i \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (42) [4] \\ &+ \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i^2} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{n_i}}{\sqrt{n_i}} \right) - v_{ie} (\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_e). \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t}, \end{aligned}$$

The two fluid model is very cumbersome and unnecessary. So it is advisable to reduce our model down to the one fluid model, by defining the global mass and charge densities, and global fluid velocity,

$$\rho = e(n_i - n_e), \mathbf{J} = e(n_i \mathbf{u}_i - n_e \mathbf{u}_e)$$

$$\rho_m = m_e n_e + m_i n_i$$

$$\mathbf{U} = \frac{m_e n_e \mathbf{u}_e + m_i n_i \mathbf{u}_i}{m_e n_e + m_i n_i} \quad (43) [4]$$

Such that we can write the electron and ion densities and the electron & ion velocities replaced as

$$\begin{aligned} n_e &= \frac{1}{m_i + m_e} \left(\rho_m - \frac{m_i}{e} \rho \right) \\ n_i &= \frac{1}{m_i + m_e} \left(\rho_m + \frac{m_e}{e} \rho \right) \quad (44) [4] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}(\rho_m - \frac{m_i}{e}\rho)\mathbf{u}_e &= \rho_m\mathbf{U} - \frac{m_i}{e}\mathbf{J} \\(\rho_m + \frac{m_e}{e}\rho)\mathbf{u}_i &= \rho_m\mathbf{U} + \frac{m_e}{e}\mathbf{J}\end{aligned}$$

Multiplying the mass continuity equations in (42) by m_e & m_i respectively and adding them, as well as multiplying the momentum conservation equations in (42) by m_en_e & m_in_i respectively, we shall get the new continuity equations, where we have used the condition of quasi neutrality to set $n_e = n_i, \rho = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial\rho_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m\mathbf{U}) &= 0 \\ \rho_m\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{U}\right) &= -\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{P}} + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{\hbar^2\rho_m}{2m_em_i}\nabla\left(\frac{\nabla^2\sqrt{\rho_m}}{\sqrt{\rho_m}}\right)\end{aligned}\quad [4]$$

Where $\tilde{\mathbf{P}} = P\mathbf{I} + \frac{m_em_in_en_i}{\rho_m}(\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i)$, in which the P is the kinetic pressure, and the latter term is the osmotic pressure; the osmotic pressure can be neglected by assuming $P_e = P_i = P/2$. We can now write the simplified one fluid model quantum magnetohydrodynamics equations as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial\rho_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m\mathbf{U}) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial\mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{U} &= -\frac{1}{\rho_m}\nabla P + \frac{1}{\rho_m}\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_em_i}\nabla\left(\frac{\nabla^2\sqrt{\rho_m}}{\sqrt{\rho_m}}\right), \\ \nabla P &= V_s^2\nabla\rho_m, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0\mathbf{J},\end{aligned}\quad (45) [4]$$

Where we assumed the equation of state adiabatic, to write the equation of pressure, where V_s to be the adiabatic speed of sound. [4]

2.4 Relevance and Consequences of Quantum Effects

To measure the strength of the quantum effects we must at first choose a lab frame, which further simplifies some of the equations of the (45). So we choose a frame, where $\mathbf{E} = -\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B}$, this frame is most useful if conductivity is approximated to be infinite, or in other words we say the plasma fluid act as a perfect fluid. The equations above can re-written as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial\rho_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m\mathbf{U}) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial\mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{U} &= -\frac{1}{\rho_m}\nabla P + \frac{1}{\rho_m\mu_0}(\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_em_i}\nabla\left(\frac{\nabla^2\sqrt{\rho_m}}{\sqrt{\rho_m}}\right), \\ \nabla P &= V_s^2\nabla\rho_m, \\ \nabla \times (\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B}) &= \frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (46) [4]$$

Now we have to compare the quantities w.r.t to a classical value of these quantities, to get a better idea when does the classical picture needed to be replaced by the quantum picture. For that we do a rescaling:

$$\bar{\rho}_m = \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_0}, \bar{\mathbf{U}} = \frac{\mathbf{U}}{V_A}, \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \frac{\mathbf{B}}{B_0} \quad [4]$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{\Omega_i \mathbf{r}}{V_A}, \bar{t} = \Omega_i t$$

where, $V_A = \left(B_0^2 / (\mu_0 \rho_0) \right)^{1/2}$ is the Alfvén velocity, and $\Omega_i = eB_0/m_i$ the ion cyclotron frequency, respectively given by

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}_m}{\partial \bar{t}} + \bar{\nabla} \cdot (\bar{\rho}_m \bar{\mathbf{U}}) = 0$$

$$\bar{\rho}_m \left(\frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{U}}}{\partial \bar{t}} + \bar{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \bar{\nabla} \bar{\mathbf{U}} \right) = -\frac{V_s^2}{V_A^2} \bar{\nabla} \bar{\rho}_m + (\bar{\nabla} \times \bar{\mathbf{B}}) \times \bar{\mathbf{B}} + \frac{H^2 \bar{\rho}_m}{2} \bar{\nabla} \left(\frac{\bar{\nabla}^2 (\bar{\rho}_m)^{1/2}}{(\bar{\rho}_m)^{1/2}} \right) \quad (48) \quad [4]$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \bar{t}} = \bar{\nabla} \times (\bar{\mathbf{U}} \times \bar{\mathbf{B}})$$

Where the H is the dimensionless parameter demonstrating quantum effects. It is given by

$$H = \frac{\hbar \Omega_i}{\sqrt{m_e m_i} V_A^2} \quad [4]$$

It can be written in terms of the equilibrium mass density ρ_0 which is itself proportional to the equilibrium number density n_0 , and the equilibrium magnetic field B_0 . Substituting V_A and mass of electron $m_e = 9.1 \times 10^{-31}$ kg, and that of ion (considering only for the Hydrogen ion (proton) to be $m_i = 1.67 \times 10^{-27}$ kg, as well as the cyclotron frequency Ω_i we get, $H = 5.44 \times 10^{-31} n_0 / B_0$. Clearly this indicates the quantum pressure will be significant only when the number density of ions and electron is nearly of the order $10^{29} - 10^{31}$.

We now calculate the order of magnitude of the magnetic field, for a particular type of quantum system by choosing the length scale defined above. In our chosen length scale, we can assume the fluid motion of plasma at equilibrium is slowly varying so that the del operator can be approximated as $\bar{\nabla} \approx \frac{1}{L}$, where the L is the characteristic length scale defined as $L = V_A \Omega_i^{-1}$, which is found to be $L = \frac{m_i}{e(\mu_0 \rho_0)^{1/2}} \sim 10^{-5}$.

Considering the special case, in which density of the plasma is uniform, such that the pressure is also constant, which is a good local approximation that can be made for a particular layer in compact objects like neutron star, considering it to have a perfect spherical density. For a steady state case, comparing the magnetic pressure and the quantum mechanical pressure terms, on the basis of order of magnitude we shall get: [5]

$$\frac{1}{\rho_m \mu_0} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} \approx \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_m}}{\sqrt{\rho_m}} \right) \text{ in the characteristic length scales, we get } \frac{1}{\rho_m \mu_0} \mathbf{B}^2 \approx \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i L^3} \left(\frac{1}{(\bar{\rho}_m)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\rho_m \mu_0} \mathbf{B}^2 \approx \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i L^3} \Rightarrow \mathbf{B}^2 \approx \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i} \frac{\rho_m \mu_0}{L^3}.$$

If we consider a neutron star system, the average magnetic field of the neutron star, of mass density ρ_m of order of 10^{17} kg/m^3 , we shall get a magnetic field strength of $B \sim 10^6 \text{ Tesla}$. This is in accordance with the experimentally observed value, which vary from $10^4 - 10^7 \text{ Tesla}$ on average for an ordinary neutron star, for a magnetar, this can go as high as up to an order of 10^{12} Tesla .

Next, we find the mechanical plasma pressure holding the neutron star together. In the slowly varying parameter approach, the pressure equation $\nabla P = V_s^2 \nabla \rho_m$, can be written in terms of characteristic length scale as $\frac{1}{L} P \approx V_s^2 \frac{1}{L} \rho_m$, OR $P \approx V_s^2 \rho_m$. For a neutron star of mass density 10^{17} kg/m^3 , and adiabatic speed of sound inside a typical neutron star being of the order of $V_s \sim 10^6 \text{ m/s}$, we get mechanical plasma pressure inside the neutron star to be of the order $P \sim 10^{29} \text{ Pascals}$, which is stupendously massive pressure, about more than a hundred trillion times the pressure at the centre of the Sun.

Figure 5: Neutron degeneracy pressure [14]

The quantum mechanical pressure, inside the neutron star can be found by the slowly varying parameter

$$\text{approximation can be found to be } \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{\rho_m}}{\sqrt{\rho_m}} \right) \approx$$

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_i} \frac{1}{L^3} \sim 10^5 \text{ Pascals. This is the degeneracy pressure}$$

due to the quantum plasma, emanating outward from the core of the neutron star, which is being hydrostatically balanced by the gravitational pressure. That is how neutron star stay stable for trillion trillions of years, until decay of baryon process become feasible and the neutron start to decay to more fundamental particles. Therefore, by the fluid model of the quantum mechanical plasma we have calculated some important results, that can be experimentally validated about such compact objects such as the neutron stars.

Chapter 3: Relativistic Magnetohydrodynamics (Flat Spacetime)

3.1 Plasma Moving with Relativistic Speeds

Till now we have developed the fluid description of the non-relativistic plasma. But in many astrophysical scenarios the non-relativistic model is insufficient to explain the plasma behaviour all together. Any cold plasma system, in which particles are moving with near light speed velocity, relative to the observer is called a relativistic plasma. Starting from the high energetic cosmic rays coming from space to relativistic jets, originating from Supermassive blackholes, there are numerous examples of relativistic plasma. In this chapter and in the next, we shall extend our fluid model to the relativistic domain, in which we shall develop a covariant theory of dynamics of fluids, under magnetohydrodynamic framework and find the conditions under which the relativistic magnetohydrodynamic model stays valid. In this chapter, we present such a formulation, restricting our attention to special relativity where we still have a “flat” geometry. In the next chapter, we shall look into the more general case in which we will develop the same for the curved geometry.

In order to model the relativistic plasmas in a continuum model, the restriction on the plasma velocities must be alleviated, by revisiting the ideal MHD equations in a frame-invariant relativistic formulation within four-dimensional space-time.

3.2 A Brief Talk on the Einsteinian Relativity and the Concept of Flat Spacetime

Theory of relativity, first put forward by Einstein in 1905, is one of the pillars of modern physics. He put forward his theory to modify the Galilean relativity, as it clearly did not agree with the Maxwell’s theory of light. Galilean addition of relative velocities saw clear violation, when measuring any observer’s velocity w.r.t. light, as by principle, Maxwell equations predicted light wave should have same speed c in all inertial frames. To keep the notion of the relativity of Galileo, still alive, theory of light wave moving through ether were put up, and it was argued that the contraction and rarefaction in the ether make up for the constant speed of light in any frame of the observer. But it was soon debunked by the famous Michelson Morley Interferometry experiment, which failed to give any evidence on the ether. Einstein, at last, came to the scene, where he astoundingly gave the idea, that, space and time themselves contract and dilate so as to keep speed of light a constant in every reference frame, and thus how space and time were found to be two different aspect of the same thing, the spacetime.

Later on, Minkowski and others put forward the mathematical framework of relativity, which became the underlying structure of any relativistic theory. The two postulates of the theory of relativity, coined by Einstein are i) Speed of Light is a constant in all inertial reference frames, and ii) Laws of Physics are equivalent in all inertial reference frames. Of course this were the postulates of the special theory of relativity, which explains anything happening in the flat spacetime.

For the equivalence of physical laws in every inertial frame, the spacetime coordinates must transform in a very special way, known as the Lorentz Transformation Rules, and any theory following this transformation rules for the coordinates is known to be a covariant theory. Suppose a frame where the spacetime coordinates of an object are (t, x, y, z) , then corresponding coordinates (t', x', y', z') of the object in an inertial frame, moving with velocity v , relative to it (denoted by the primed coordinate system) are given the Lorentz Transformation rules given below

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}' &= \mathbf{x} + \frac{\Gamma-1}{v^2} \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{x} - \Gamma \mathbf{v} t \\ t' &= \Gamma \left(t - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{x} \right), \Gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \quad (49) [6] \end{aligned}$$

Figure 6: Lorentz transformation [15]

where, the Lorentz factor is defined as $\Gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}}$. In tensorial notation the same can be represented as $X^{\alpha'} = L_{\alpha}^{\alpha'} X^{\alpha}$, where, the transformation matrix is given by

$$L_{\alpha}^{\alpha'} = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma & -\Gamma \frac{v_1}{c} & -\Gamma \frac{v_2}{c} & -\Gamma \frac{v_3}{c} \\ -\Gamma \frac{v_1}{c} & 1 + (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_1^2}{v^2} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_1 v_2}{v^2} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_1 v_3}{v^2} \\ -\Gamma \frac{v_2}{c} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_1 v_2}{v^2} & 1 + (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_2^2}{v^2} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_2 v_3}{v^2} \\ -\Gamma \frac{v_3}{c} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_1 v_3}{v^2} & (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_2 v_3}{v^2} & 1 + (\Gamma - 1) \frac{v_3^2}{v^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (50)$$

[6]

We can however use without any loss of generality, the Lorentz boost form of (50), where we restrict the velocity of the primed frame, w.r.t. observer frame in the x axis, such that the Lorentz transformation can be given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} ct' \\ x'_1 \\ x'_2 \\ x'_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma & -\Gamma v_1/c & 0 & 0 \\ -\Gamma v_1/c & \Gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} ct \\ x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (51) [6]$$

It can finally be inferred from (51) that the square of the vectors of both the frame must always remain invariant.

$$-c^2 t^2 + x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 = -c^2 t'^2 + x_1'^2 + x_2'^2 + x_3'^2 \quad (52)$$

Thus, the Lorentz transformation is just a rotation to the vector in Minkowski Space, which follow the metric

$$ds^2 = -c^2 t^2 + x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 \quad (53)$$

We can then by the second postulate of relativity, find that every physical quantity, therefore must transform similarly, and must have an invariant. Such physical quantities are called four vectors. The most common one of them is the four velocity. We now consider the path traced in space-time by a single particle, which we will call the world line of this particle. Time progression as experienced by this particle is referred to as its “proper time”. This proper time τ is measured by an ideal clock in the particle’s local rest frame, i.e. in a reference frame moving along with the particle. Introducing a local Lorentzian reference frame with orthogonal coordinates X^α , the particle four-velocity is then given by $U^\alpha \equiv \frac{dX^\alpha}{d\tau}$, where $dX^\alpha \equiv (cdt, dx_1, dx_2, dx_3)^T$ measures the proper distance along each coordinate direction traversed in the proper time interval $d\tau$. The transformations given by Eq. (50) can thus be understood as follows: two reference frames L and L' each introduce their set of basis vectors e_α and $e_{\alpha'}$, respectively. The matrix $L^\alpha_{\alpha'}$ quantifies how each basis vector e_α can be written as a linear combination of the other set of basis vectors, namely $e_\alpha = L^\alpha_{\alpha'} e_{\alpha'}$. Note that the double appearance of the Greek index α' implies a summation, and we will from now on adopt this Einstein convention. The frame-independent four-position vector X is then clearly

$$\mathbf{X} = X^\alpha e_\alpha = X^\alpha L^\alpha_{\alpha'} e_{\alpha'} = X^{\alpha'} e_{\alpha'} \quad (54)$$

The invariant being

$$\mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{X} = (X^\alpha e_\alpha) \cdot (X^\beta e_\beta) = g_{\alpha\beta} X^\alpha X^\beta = X^\alpha X_\alpha \quad (55)$$

The four momentum is given similarly by

$$P^\alpha = m_0 U^\alpha \quad (56) [6]$$

The invariant quantities for 4-velocity and 4-momentum found to be

$$U^\alpha U_\alpha = -c^2 \text{ \& } P^\alpha P_\alpha = E^2 - p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \text{ (57) [6]}$$

where, E is relativistic energy and p is relativistic momentum : $E = \Gamma m_0 c^2$ and

$\mathbf{p} = \Gamma m_0 \mathbf{v}$, m_0 being the rest mass, which is the particle mass in the particle's rest frame.

So in relativity, we see mass and energy are two sides of the same coin, as it is entombed in the above momentum-energy relation (57), perhaps the most important relation in all relativity.

3.3 Relativistic Fluid Dynamics

For fluid description of the plasma we need to find the momentum, energy and mass conservation equations of the fluid. In relativity, mass energy are the different manifestations of the same thing, as we have seen in the previous section. So in this case, we need to find the conservation relation of momentum-energy, directly from the four dimensional momentum-energy stress tensor, which has to be covariant in every inertial frame, as this time unlike in the non-relativistic case, they have to be unifiedly conserved. We then find the transformed stress tensor in the laboratory frame, from the Lorentz transformation and have the required conservation equations of the hydrodynamics.

We can now formulate the governing conservation laws in four-dimensional spacetime. We begin with particle conservation. The proper density ρ is the mass per unit volume as seen in the rest frame of the gas. When we indicate the number density per unit volume in this frame by n_0 , we have

$$\rho = m_0 n_0 \text{ (58)}$$

In the inertial Lorentzian frame where the gas is seen to move with velocity v, volumes differ due to the length contraction effect. As a result, the number density will be $n = \Gamma n_0$. A convenient variable to quantify the “density” in this “laboratory” frame is $D = \Gamma m_0 n_0 = m_0 n = \Gamma \rho$. It should be noted that the actual lab frame density is ΓD , due to the mass increase $m(v) = \Gamma m_0$, but we will loosely refer to D as the density. Particle number conservation is then generally expressed by the vanishing divergence of the four-vector ρU^α , namely

$$\partial_\alpha (\rho U^\alpha) = 0 \text{ (59) [6]}$$

Because energy and momentum need to be treated as a single physical entity, the classical (three-)momentum and energy conservation laws will be unified in a conservation law in four dimensions, involving the vanishing divergence of a four-tensor. This four-tensor is the

stress–energy tensor which we will denote in contravariant components with $T^{\alpha\beta}$. Its components contain

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{00} & T^{0i} \\ T^{i0} & T^{ij} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{energy density} & \text{energy flux} \\ \text{momentum flux} & \text{stresses} \end{pmatrix} \quad (60) [6]$$

In the rest frame of the fluid, explicit expressions for its components are easily given, since fluxes vanish there. The energy density $T^{0'0'}$ contains both a rest mass and an internal energy contribution. Writing the specific internal energy in the fluid frame as, the expression for the energy density is $T^{0'0'} = \rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon$. And the isotropic pressure corresponds to stresses $T^{i'j'} = p\mathbf{I}$. When we now transform back to the laboratory frame where the gas moves with velocity \mathbf{v} , we compute [6]

$$T^{\alpha\beta} = (L^{-1})_{\alpha'}^{\alpha} (L^{-1})_{\beta'}^{\beta} T^{\alpha'\beta'} \quad (61) [6]$$

From the Lorentz transformation relation for 4-vector (54), we can determine that

$$(L^{-1})_{\alpha'}^{\alpha} = \frac{U^{\alpha}}{U^{\alpha'}} \quad (62)$$

Since the prime frame in here is chosen to be at rest then the 4-velocity corresponding to the frame will be $U^{\alpha} = (c, 0, 0, 0)$, then the eq. (61) yields

$$T^{\alpha\beta} = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p) \frac{U^{\alpha}U^{\beta}}{c^2} + p g^{\alpha\beta}. \quad (63) [6]$$

Using the transformed 4-velocity in lab frame $U^{\alpha} = (c\Gamma, \Gamma\mathbf{v})^T$ we find the stress tensor in lab frame to be

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} T^{00} & T^{0i} \\ T^{i0} & T^{ij} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2 - p & (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}/c \\ (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}/c & \rho\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v} + p\mathbf{I} + (\rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v}/c^2 \end{pmatrix} \\ &\equiv \begin{pmatrix} \tau_g + Dc^2 & \frac{\mathbf{S}_g}{c} \\ \frac{\mathbf{S}_g}{c} & \frac{\mathbf{S}_g\mathbf{v}}{c^2} + p\mathbf{I} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (64) [6]$$

In terms of the variables τ_g (the total energy density in the lab frame, minus the rest mass contribution), and the three-vector \mathbf{S}_g (the relativistic energy flux), the divergence of the stress–energy tensor is then written as follows. The temporal part, i.e. the equation $\partial_{\alpha}T^{0\alpha} = 0$, and the spatial part $\partial_{\alpha}T^{i\alpha} = 0$ will yield [6]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\tau_g + Dc^2) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{S}_g = 0 \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}_g}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{S}_g\mathbf{v} + pc^2\mathbf{I}) = 0 \quad (65) [6]$$

3.4 Relativistic Magnetohydrodynamics

Having found the fluid equations governing the fluid motion, we now need to find how the fluid would behave in the presence of the electromagnetic field, and thus find the corresponding mass and energy-momentum equations for the electromagnetic plasma, much the same way we did it for the general fluid. When dealing with plasmas, with charged particle constituents, the electric and magnetic fields generated by static as well as moving charged particles introduce particle accelerations due to electrostatic fields and the Lorentz force. The electric and magnetic fields themselves are governed by the Maxwell equations. However, static charges which act as sources for electric fields in one Lorentzian reference frame will be moving charges, i.e. currents, leading to magnetic fields in another frame in relative motion. The combined six components of both three-vectors will in fact form the six independent tensor components of an asymmetric four-tensor of rank two. In what follows, we revisit the Maxwell equations in the appropriate tensorial formulation applicable in space-time. We then generalize the stress–energy tensor to include electromagnetic field contributions. Finally, we specify the governing equations for relativistic plasma dynamics for perfectly conducting plasmas, where the electric field in the co-moving frame vanishes. This then yields the ideal MHD equations in special relativity. [6]

The Maxwell equations in the tensorial notation can be written as

$$\partial_\beta F^{\alpha\beta} = J^\alpha. \quad \partial_\beta F^{*\alpha\beta} = 0. \quad (66)$$

where, $F^{\alpha\beta}$ & $F^{*\alpha\beta}$ are the Maxwell field strength tensor and its dual.

$$F^{\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & E_1/c & E_2/c & E_3/c \\ -E_1/c & 0 & B_3 & -B_2 \\ -E_2/c & -B_3 & 0 & B_1 \\ -E_3/c & B_2 & -B_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$F^{*\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & B_1/c & B_2/c & B_3/c \\ -B_1/c & 0 & -E_3/c^2 & E_2/c^2 \\ -B_2/c & E_3/c^2 & 0 & -E_1/c^2 \\ -B_3/c & -E_2/c^2 & E_1/c^2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (67)$$

Now in this case the electromagnetic field also has an energy density and momentum density, as well as apply a stress, in addition to the mechanical stress of the plasma fluid. Thus we have to find the electromagnetic field 4-d energy momentum tensor, in the laboratory frame in this case as well. If $F^{\alpha\beta}$ & its dual are measured at laboratory frame, the electric and magnetic field in fluid's rest frame is found to be

$$e^\alpha = F^{\alpha\beta} U_\beta \text{ \& } b^\alpha = F^{*\alpha\beta} U_\beta \quad (68)$$

Now we need to find the fields in the lab frame, for which we can use the tensor identity

$$F_{\mu\nu}^* = -\frac{1}{2c} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}. \quad (69)$$

And the Levi-Civita relations

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} &= -e^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} \\ \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\mu\nu} \epsilon_{\alpha\gamma\lambda\kappa} &= -\delta_\gamma^\beta \delta_\lambda^\mu \delta_\kappa^\nu + \delta_\gamma^\beta \delta_\kappa^\mu \delta_\lambda^\nu + \delta_\lambda^\beta \delta_\gamma^\mu \delta_\kappa^\nu - \delta_\lambda^\beta \delta_\kappa^\mu \delta_\gamma^\nu \\ &\quad -\delta_\kappa^\beta \delta_\gamma^\mu \delta_\lambda^\nu + \delta_\kappa^\beta \delta_\lambda^\mu \delta_\gamma^\nu = -\delta_{\gamma\lambda\kappa}^{\beta\mu\nu} = - \begin{vmatrix} \delta_\gamma^\beta & \delta_\lambda^\beta & \delta_\kappa^\beta \\ \delta_\gamma^\mu & \delta_\lambda^\mu & \delta_\kappa^\mu \\ \delta_\gamma^\nu & \delta_\lambda^\nu & \delta_\kappa^\nu \end{vmatrix} \quad (70) [6] \\ \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\mu\nu} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta\lambda\kappa} &= -2\delta_{\lambda\kappa}^{\mu\nu}, \\ \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\mu\nu} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta\mu\kappa} &= -6\delta_\kappa^\nu, \end{aligned}$$

With (69) & (70), we can then rewrite 68 as

$$\begin{aligned} F^{\alpha\beta} &= -\frac{1}{c} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} b_\mu U_\nu - \frac{1}{c^2} (e^\alpha U^\beta - e^\beta U^\alpha) \\ F^{*\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{c^2} (U^\alpha b^\beta - U^\beta b^\alpha) + \frac{1}{2c^3} \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\mu\nu} (e_\mu U_\nu - e_\nu U_\mu) \quad (71) \end{aligned}$$

These are the fields in the lab frame, which we shall now use to find the energy momentum tensor of the fields. The classical Langrangian of the EM field is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{EM}} = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{c} j_\mu A_\mu \quad (72)$$

The energy momentum tensor in the classical field theory is defined as the

$$T^{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial(\partial_\mu A_\alpha)} \partial^\nu A_\alpha - g^{\mu\nu} \mathcal{L} \quad (73)$$

which is found to be, after substitution of the Langrangian in (73), and simplifying

$$T_{em}^{\alpha\beta} = F_\gamma^\alpha F^{\beta\gamma} - \frac{1}{4} g^{\alpha\beta} F_{\gamma\delta} F^{\gamma\delta} \quad (74) [6]$$

Now we can always choose the lab frame, where the tensor in(71) simplifies, thus, we choose a lab frame, in which e^α vanishes, or $\mathbf{E} = -\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$. Such that (71) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} F^{\alpha\beta} &= -\frac{1}{c} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} b_\mu U_\nu \\ F^{*\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{c^2} (U^\alpha b^\beta - U^\beta b^\alpha) \quad (75) [6] \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the fields found in (75) in the eq. (74), we get

$$T_{em}^{\alpha\beta} = b^\alpha b_\alpha \frac{U^\alpha U^\beta}{c^2} + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2} g^{\alpha\beta} - b^\alpha b^\beta \quad (76) [6]$$

Where, it can be recognized that $b^\alpha b_\alpha = \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}$ is the relativistic form of the magnetic pressure. In matrix form it can be written as

$$T_{em}^{\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}B^2 + \frac{1}{2c^2}[B^2v^2 - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2] & \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} \\ \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} & \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})B\mathbf{v}}{c^2} + \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}\mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B}}{c^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (77) [6]$$

Now the we are in the position to derive the ideal relativistic MHD equations. The sum of mechanical stress energy and the electromagnetic field stress energy tensor has to be conserved

$$\partial_\beta (T_{pl}^{\alpha\beta} + T_{em}^{\alpha\beta}) = 0 \quad (78) [6]$$

The total MHD Energy Momentum Tensor is found to be, thus:

$$T_{total}^{\alpha\beta} = T_{pl}^{\alpha\beta} + T_{em}^{\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}B^2 + \frac{1}{2c^2}[B^2v^2 - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2] + (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2 - p & \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}/c \\ \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}/c & \frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})B\mathbf{v}}{c^2} + \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}\mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}}{2\Gamma^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B}}{c^2} + \rho\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v} + p\mathbf{I} + (\rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v}/c^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (79) [6]$$

The temporal and spatial parts of the conservation equation gives

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_0 T_{total}^{\alpha 0} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2}B^2 + \frac{1}{2c^2}[B^2v^2 - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2] + (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2 - p \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}}{c} \right) = 0 \quad (80) \\ \partial_0 T_{total}^{\alpha 0} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}}{c} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})B\mathbf{v}}{c^2} + \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}\mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}}{2\Gamma^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B}}{c^2} + \rho\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v} + p\mathbf{I} + (\rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v}/c^2 \right) = 0 \quad (81) [6] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the equations of MHD under relativistic framework are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2}B^2 + \frac{1}{2c^2}[B^2v^2 - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2] + (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2 - p \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}}{c} \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}}{c} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2v - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})B\mathbf{v}}{c^2} + \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}\mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}}{2\Gamma^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B}}{c^2} + \rho\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v} + p\mathbf{I} + (\rho\epsilon + p)\Gamma^2\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v}/c^2 \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial D}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (D\mathbf{v}) &= 0 \\ \partial_\beta F^{\alpha\beta} = J^\alpha. \quad \partial_\beta F^{*\alpha\beta} = 0. & \quad (82) [6] \end{aligned}$$

3.5 Validity of the Relativistic MHD model and the classical limit

If we Taylor expand the Lorentz factor term as $\Gamma \cong 1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + \frac{3v^4}{8c^4} + \dots$

If $v \ll c$, we can ignore all the higher powers of v above 2nd order, such that $\Gamma \approx 1$. So in the limit $v \ll c$, the momentum and the energy conservation equation becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + \frac{1}{2c^2} [B^2 v^2 - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2] + (\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p) \Gamma^2 - p \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2 \mathbf{v} - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p) \Gamma^2 \mathbf{v}}{c} \right) &= 0 \\ \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + (\rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon) \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{(\rho c^2) \mathbf{v}}{c} \right) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{B^2 \mathbf{v} - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B}}{c} + \frac{(\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p) \Gamma^2 \mathbf{v}}{c} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{B^2 \mathbf{v} - (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B} \mathbf{v}}{c^2} + \frac{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\Gamma^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2} \mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B} \mathbf{B}}{2\Gamma^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{v} \mathbf{B}}{c^2} + \rho \Gamma^2 \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} + p \mathbf{I} + (\rho \epsilon + p) \Gamma^2 \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} / c^2 \right) &= 0 \\ \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + (\rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon) \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + (\rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon) \right) \mathbf{v} + \left(\mathbf{p} + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \right) \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B} \right) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

which are the ideal MHD conservation equations. If we Taylor expand Γ and keep up to 2nd order terms, the momentum and the energy conservation equations can be separated into relativistic and non-relativistic terms as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + (\rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon) \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 + (\rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon) \right) \mathbf{v} + \left(\mathbf{p} + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \right) \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2} + \right. \\ \left. (\rho \epsilon) \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + p \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} / c^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2} + (\rho \epsilon) \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + p \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} / c^2 \right) \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (83) \end{aligned}$$

Where relativistic terms are identified to be $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2} + (\rho \epsilon) \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + p \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} / c^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2} + (\rho \epsilon) \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + p \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v} / c^2 \right)$. The relativistic pressure, internal energy and the magnetic field terms can be written as

$$\mathbf{p}_{rel} \approx \mathbf{p} + \frac{p \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v}}{c^2}, \quad \mathbf{B}_{rel}^2 \approx \frac{1}{2} B^2 + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}, \quad \rho \epsilon_{rel} \approx (\rho \epsilon) + (\rho \epsilon) \frac{v^2}{2c^2}$$

It can be noted thereof that, as the plasma approaches speed of light, the internal energy, mechanical pressure and the magnetic pressure increases by higher and higher order terms of the Taylor expansion of the Lorentz factor.

The mechanical pressure \mathbf{p}_{rel} will increase by a factor of almost the fraction, approximated to second order term in the Lorentz factor's Taylor series). If speed of relativistic jet is say 50% of the speed of the light $\mathbf{p}_{rel} \approx \mathbf{p} \left(1 + \frac{v \mathbf{v}}{c^2} \right) = \mathbf{p} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4} \right) = \frac{5\mathbf{p}}{4}$, or the pressure increases almost 25%.

Similarly, the magnetic field pressure will increase by $\approx \frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B})^2}{c^2}$. If we take the velocity of the fluid exactly perpendicular to the magnetic field, we can write the magnetic field as

$$\frac{\mathbf{B}_{rel}^2}{2} \approx \frac{1}{2} B^2 + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \frac{v^2 \sin^2 90^\circ}{c^2} \approx \frac{1}{2} B^2 \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) = \frac{5\frac{1}{2} B^2}{4}, \text{ also by 25\%. The same is true for the internal energy.}$$

The density of the relativistic fluid is also increased $D = \Gamma\rho \approx \rho \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + \frac{3v^4}{8c^4} + \dots \right)$

If the relativistic jet travel at 50% speed of the light the density increases approximately by 14.8%, if we keep terms in the Taylor expansion of Γ up to 4th order. This increase in the

Figure 7: Relativistic Jet captured in space [17]

mass density is the direct consequence of the energy- mass equivalence postulate of the relativity, due to which the kinetic energy gets converted to the rest mass energy, as the relativistic jet approaches speed of light. Thus we encounter an increase in the stress and mass of the relativistic jet, when it approaches the speed of light. This increase is the fundamental reason, because of which none of the particles with non-zero rest mass, can travel at the speed of light, as the rest mass of the particle will be infinite, if $v = c$, as the Taylor series of Lorentz factor

diverges.

Chapter 4: Relativistic Plasma in Curved Spacetime

4.1 Curved Spacetime & Motion of Plasma in it

In the last chapter we developed the model for the flat spacetime, now we are about to extend the same relativistic framework to curved spacetime. Einstein theory of general relativity had opened many doors for astronomers to explain quite a lot of phenomenon, encountered by us in the cosmos, which would have been impossible to explain otherwise. The general relativity theory is the general case of the special theory of relativity, discussed in the previous chapter. It was put forward in necessity to explain the theory of gravity; according to the Newtonian principles, the gravity predicted to be propagating at infinite speed, which the special theory of relativity doesn't allow. Einstein surprisingly found out that, as the laws of physics were valid equivalently in all inertial reference frame, it was valid as well in all non-inertial reference frames, as it is in the case of gravity, as a frame in which gravity is perceived is an accelerated frame of reference. He also found that this is due to the fact that acceleration (rate

Figure 8: Riemannian geometry visualized [16]

of change of momentum) or mechanical stress-energy of any kind has equivalent gravitational effect as mass, which also clearly satisfied the results of the special theory of relativity, in which mass and the energy are predicted to be equivalent. So he argued that just like covariant coordinate transformation rule was applied to the coordinates of a particle in an inertial frame, much the same way, there has to be covariant rule of

transformation rules for the coordinates of the particle, in the non-inertial frame. To his amazement it indicates that the transformation rule from an inertial frame to a non-inertial frame, (where gravity is present), showed the spacetime coordinate transformation become non-linear in the non-inertial frame, or in other words the non-inertial frame, where gravity is present due to energy-mass content, has a curved geometry. The beauty of the simplicity of the theory, is that the entire postulate of the general theory can be written in one sentence as it was most famously put forward: "Matter and energy tell space how to curve, and the curved spacetime tells matter how to move." The mathematics of the theory was soon developed by mathematicians like David Hilbert, who used the Riemannian geometry for the formulation

and derived the Einstein Field equations relating the Spacetime curvature to the total mass-energy stress and flux content in the spacetime. It is given by

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu} \quad (84)$$

where, the $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Riemann curvature tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, R is the curvature scalar, $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy momentum or stress-energy tensor.

In cosmos, all heavenly bodies, every matter objects, including our own bodies warp spacetime around it. The effect only is noticeable for a very massive body, due to the fact that the energy scale has to be quite large because the strength of the gravity is very weak (G has a very small value of $6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$). For objects of comparable size as our star, and planets and less, the general theory of relativity reduces to the Newtonian theory of gravitation, which is called the Newtonian limit.

In space, there are lots of objects, with massive size, which warp spacetime around them considerably, and we have to formulate the dynamics of any particle in their vicinity, using the general theory of relativity, as the relativistic effect cannot be ignored in this regard. These objects include neutron stars, and black holes. Behaviour of plasma, around these objects in various situational context, need a general relativistic approach to study them. The phenomena include but not limited to stellar core-collapse, in case of a supernova, black hole formation and accretion disk, composed of hot and dense plasma moving in a curved geodesic, ultimately bordering to the event horizon of the black hole, jet formation in the supermassive black holes, gamma ray bursts, and coalescing neutron star/blackholes. In all of the mentioned cases, one need a relativistic covariant theory of fluids, such is in the previous chapter but for a curved metric. In this chapter we develop such fluid dynamics. [7]

4.2 3+1 ADM Formalism-the Form of the Metric of Spacetime

We will follow the equivalent approach for the curved spacetime, the same, which we have followed for the flat spacetime, but in this case we have to define a metric for the curved spacetime, first. After that, like the previous case, we find the 4d energy-momentum tensor for the fluid and for the electromagnetic fields, and write down the momentum-energy conservation and mass conservation equations. Now one the most common approach to define a metric is by the approach, introduced by R Arnowitt, S Deser, & C W Misner, in the early 1960s, known as the 3+1 ADM Formalism. This has become one of the most useful

Figure 9: Foliation of the spacetime \mathcal{M} by a family of space-like hypersurfaces [8]

four-dimensional spacetime by three-dimensional surfaces (hypersurfaces). These hypersurfaces have to be space-like, so that the metric induced on them by the Lorentzian spacetime metric [signature $(-,+,+,+)$] is Riemannian [signature $(+,+,+)$]. From the mathematical point of view, this procedure allows to formulate the problem of resolution of Einstein equations as a Cauchy problem with constraints. From the pedestrian point of view, it amounts to a decomposition of spacetime into “space” + “time”, so that one manipulates only time-varying tensor fields in the “ordinary” three-dimensional space, where the standard scalar product is Riemannian. Notice that this space + time splitting is not an a priori structure of general relativity but relies on the somewhat arbitrary choice of a time coordinate. [8]

Figure 10: Coordinates (x_i) on the hypersurfaces t : each line $x^i = \text{constant}$ cuts across the foliation $\Sigma_t \in \mathcal{R}$ [8]

tool, in study of the GRMHD, because gives us a ‘decomposed’ 3+1 time (1 dimension) and space (3 dimension) like approach, where space is separately dealt with, apart from time, for a local point of view, although globally, the spacetime is considered a single entity. This makes the numerical simulation of the Einstein field equation and the GRMHD equations very much easier to do. The 3+1 formalism is an approach to general relativity and to Einstein equations that relies on the slicing of the

According to the ADM formalism, the spacetime manifold \mathcal{M} is assumed to be globally hyperbolic and to admit a foliation by 3-dimensional space-like hypersurfaces Σ_t parameterized by the parameter $t \in \mathcal{R}$: $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{R} \times \Sigma_t$. The future-pointing 4-vector n orthonormal to Σ_t is then proportional to the gradient of t : $\mathbf{n} = -\alpha \nabla t$, where α

is chosen following the normalization $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{n} = -1$. Introducing a coordinate basis

$\{\mathbf{e}_{(\mu)}\} = \{\mathbf{e}_{(0)}, \mathbf{e}_{(i)}\}$ of 4-vectors and choosing the normalization of the time-like coordinate basis 4-vector $\mathbf{e}_{(0)}$ to be $\mathbf{e}_{(0)} \cdot \nabla t = 1$ with the other three basis 4-vectors to be space-like (i.e. tangent to the hypersurface: $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}_{(i)} = 0$), then the decomposition of \mathbf{n} into the basis $\{\mathbf{e}_{(\mu)}\}$ is

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{e}_{(0)}}{\alpha} + \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \quad (85) [8]$$

where $\beta = \beta^i \mathbf{e}_{(i)}$ is a purely spatial vector called the shift vector, since it describes how the spatial coordinates shift when moving from a slice Σ_t to another $\Sigma_{t'}$. The function is called lapse and describes the rate of advance of time along the time-like unit-vector \mathbf{n} normal to a space-like hypersurface Σ_t . Defining $\gamma_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_{\mu\nu} + n_\mu n_\nu$ to be the spatial part of the 4-metric, so that $\gamma \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ and $\gamma_{\mu\nu}$ is the 3-metric of the hypersurfaces, the line element in the 3+1 splitting reads

$$ds^2 = \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta X^\alpha X^\beta = -(\alpha^2 - \beta^i \beta_i) dt^2 + 2\beta_i dx^i dt + \gamma_{ij} dx^i dx^j \quad [8]$$

The metric thus can be written as

$$g^{\alpha\beta} = \mathbf{e}^\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}^\beta = \begin{pmatrix} g^{00} & g^{0j} \\ g^{i0} & g^{ij} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{\alpha^2} & \frac{\beta^j}{\alpha^2} \\ \frac{\beta^i}{\alpha^2} & \gamma^{ij} - \frac{\beta^i \beta^j}{\alpha^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta = \begin{pmatrix} g_{00} & g_{0j} \\ g_{i0} & g_{ij} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -(\alpha^2 - \beta^i \beta_i) & \beta_j \\ \beta_i & \gamma_{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (86) [8]$$

The four velocity has defined in section 3.2(See page no. 23), is given by $U^\alpha \equiv \frac{dX^\alpha}{d\tau}$, in the fluid rest frame. The three velocity of the fluid measured in the lab frame is given by

$$v^i \equiv \frac{dx^i}{dt} = \frac{\frac{dx^i}{d\tau}}{\frac{dX^0}{d\tau}} = \frac{U^i}{U^0} = \frac{g^i_\mu u^\mu}{g^0_\nu u^\nu} = \frac{\gamma^i_\mu u^\mu}{-\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}} \quad (87) [9]$$

Now since \mathbf{n} is the normal to the hypersurface, we recognize $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ to be the relative Lorentz factor, as $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \frac{dX^0}{d\tau} = \frac{cdt}{d\tau} = c\Gamma = \frac{c}{\sqrt{(1-v^2)}}$. Precisely for the metric given in the eq. (85),

$$\Gamma = \alpha u^t \quad (88) [9]$$

Thus for the lab frame we can choose the new basis as $\mathbf{e}_{(\lambda)} = \{\mathbf{n}, \partial_i\}$, which are much more convenient, as the time components of the stress energy tensor, as we will see will get much easier to handle.

4.3 Derivation of the GRMHD Conservation Equations Using the ADM Formalism

The stress energy total energy momentum tensor is the sum of the fluid stress energy tensor and electromagnetic field energy stress tensor, which have respectively derived in eq. (63) and in eq. (76) (See page no. 27 & 29, respectively). So total energy momentum tensor is

$$T_{total}^{\alpha\beta} = T_{pl}^{\alpha\beta} + T_{em}^{\alpha\beta} = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \frac{u^\alpha u^\beta}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) g^{\alpha\beta} - b^\alpha b^\beta \quad (89) [9]$$

The quantities measured in the lab frame are

$$\begin{aligned} T_{total}^{00} &= T_{total}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{e}_0 \cdot \mathbf{e}_0) = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \frac{u^\alpha \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot u^\beta \mathbf{e}_0}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) g^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot \mathbf{e}_0 - b^\alpha \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot b^\beta \mathbf{e}_0 = \\ &(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \frac{u^\alpha \mathbf{n} \cdot u^\beta \mathbf{n}}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{n} - b^\alpha \mathbf{n} \cdot b^\beta \mathbf{n} = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \end{aligned} \quad [9]$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{total}^{0j} &= T_{total}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{e}_0 \cdot \mathbf{e}_j) = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \frac{u^\alpha \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot u^\beta \mathbf{e}_j}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) g^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot \mathbf{e}_j - b^\alpha \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot b^\beta \mathbf{e}_j = \\ &(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 \cdot v_j + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}_j - b^\alpha \mathbf{e}_0 \cdot b^\beta \mathbf{e}_j = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 \cdot v_j - \alpha b^0 b_j \end{aligned} \quad [9]$$

Since from relation (85), $u_i \mathbf{e}_j = (\Gamma c, \Gamma v^i)$.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{total}^{ij} &= T_{total}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j) = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \frac{u^\alpha \mathbf{e}_i \cdot u^\beta \mathbf{e}_j}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) g^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j - b^\alpha \mathbf{e}_i \cdot b^\beta \mathbf{e}_j = \\ &(\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 v_j v_i + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) \delta_j^i - b^i b_j \quad (90) [9] \end{aligned}$$

So the energy momentum tensor in the matrix form can be written as

$$T_{total}^{\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau_t + Dc^2 & \frac{S_t v}{c} \\ \frac{S_t v}{c} & \frac{S_t v}{c^2} + \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) \mathbf{I} - b^\alpha b^\beta \end{pmatrix} \quad (91) [9]$$

Where, we define the total energy density τ_t & flux density S_t as

$$\tau_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \quad \& \quad S_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha) \Gamma^2 \cdot v_j - \alpha b^0 b_j \quad (92) [9]$$

Now the conservation of energy momentum tensor can be written as the following

$$\nabla_\nu T_{total} g^{\alpha\beta} = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \nabla_{\nu} T_{total} g^{\alpha\beta} + T_{total} \nabla_{\nu} g^{\alpha\beta} = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} T^0}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} T^{\beta} (v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha})}{\partial x_{\mu}} \right) + T_{\mu\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_{\mu}} - \Gamma_{\delta}^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta} \right) = 0 \quad (93) \quad [9] \end{aligned}$$

Where, as it can be noted the normal derivative has been replaced by the covariant derivative in response to the non-linear metric tensor, whose derivative now contributes to the conservation as opposed to the flat spacetime case. Substituting the components of T from (89) in (92), we will get the following conservation equations in the curved spacetime for the plasma, as follows, respectively for the temporal and spatial parts of the tensor, as well as the mass conservation equation:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} \mathbf{S}^{\beta}}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} \left(\mathbf{S}_j \left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right) + p^* \delta_j^i - b_j (\Gamma b^i - \alpha b^0 u^i) / \Gamma \right)}{\partial x_{\mu}} \right) + T_{\mu\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_{\mu}} - \Gamma_{\delta}^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta} \right) = 0 \\ &\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} \tau_t}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} \left(\tau_t \left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right) + p^* v^i - \alpha b^0 (\Gamma b^i - \alpha b^0 u^i) / \Gamma \right)}{\partial x_{\mu}} \right) + T_{\mu 0} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_{\mu}} - \Gamma_0^{\mu\alpha} \alpha \right) = 0 \\ &\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} D}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} D \left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right)}{\partial x_{\mu}} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

(94) [9]

where, we have defined $p^* = p + \frac{b^{\alpha} b_{\alpha}}{2}$. These are the energy and momentum conservation equations and the mass conservation equations in the curved spacetime, respectively where

$$\tau_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p + b^{\alpha} b_{\alpha}) \Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{b^{\alpha} b_{\alpha}}{2} \right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \quad \& \quad \mathbf{S}_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p + b^{\alpha} b_{\alpha}) \Gamma^2. \mathbf{v}_j - \alpha b^0 b_j$$

as defined in (91).

4.4 Maxwell Equations in the Curved Spacetime, and Evolution of Magnetic Field

Choosing a lab frame, where the equations of fields simplifies, we had chosen the frame where $\vec{E} = -\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$. We got the components of the electromagnetic field strength tensor and its dual, (refer Eq. (75), page no. 29)

$$\begin{aligned} F^{\alpha\beta} &= -\frac{1}{c} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} b_{\mu} U_{\nu} \\ F^{*\alpha\beta} &= \frac{1}{c^2} (U^{\alpha} b^{\beta} - U^{\beta} b^{\alpha}) \quad [9] \end{aligned}$$

From Eq. 86, we can substitute the 4-velocity for our chosen metric to be $U^{\mu} = \left(v^{\mu} - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right)$, then the Maxwell equation can be written as $\nabla_{\nu}^* F^{\mu\nu} = 0$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial(\sqrt{\gamma}B^i)}{\partial x^i} &= 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\sqrt{\gamma}B^i) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\{\sqrt{\gamma}[(\alpha v^i - \beta^i)B^j - (\alpha v^j - \beta^j)B^i]\},\end{aligned}\quad (95) [9]$$

are respectively the temporal part and the spatial part of the Maxwell equation, which are relativistic analog of the non-relativistic Maxwell equations $\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B})$ & $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$.

Thus the GRMHD equations for a plasma motion in a curved spacetime are

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}}\left(\frac{\partial\sqrt{\gamma}\mathbf{S}^\beta}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial\sqrt{-g}\left(\mathbf{S}_j\left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha}\right) + p^*\delta_j^i - b_j(\Gamma b^i - \alpha b^0 u^i)/\Gamma\right)}{\partial x_i}\right) + T_{\mu\alpha}\left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_\delta^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta}\right) = 0$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}}\left(\frac{\partial\sqrt{\gamma}\tau_t}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial\sqrt{-g}\left(\tau_t\left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha}\right) + p^*v^i - \alpha b^0(\Gamma b^i - \alpha b^0 u^i)/\Gamma\right)}{\partial x_i}\right) + T_{\mu\alpha}\left(\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_0^{\mu\alpha}\alpha\right) = 0$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}}\left(\frac{\partial\sqrt{\gamma}\mathbf{D}}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial\sqrt{-g}\mathbf{D}\left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha}\right)}{\partial x_i}\right) = 0$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\sqrt{\gamma}B^i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\{\sqrt{\gamma}[(\alpha v^i - \beta^i)B^j - (\alpha v^j - \beta^j)B^i]\}$$

$$\frac{\partial(\sqrt{\gamma}B^i)}{\partial x^i} = 0$$

(96) [9]

4.5 Validity of the GRMHD Model and the Required Conditions for Consideration of Effect of Curvature

The non-relativistic form of the momentum and energy conservation equations read as (when the system is considered adiabatic, as discussed in the Chapter 1

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho\mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \left[\rho\mathbf{v}\mathbf{v} + \left(p + \frac{1}{2}B^2\right)\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}\right] &= 0, \\ p &= (\gamma - 1)\rho\epsilon, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 + \rho\epsilon + \frac{1}{2}B^2\right) + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + B^2\right)\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}\right] &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0.\end{aligned}\quad (97)$$

Not to our surprise, when we approach the flat spacetime limit, as our metric in (85) approaches Minkowski spacetime metric

$$\begin{pmatrix} -N^2 + \beta_k\beta^k & \beta_j \\ \beta_i & \gamma_{ij} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{ij} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\tau_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha)\Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{b^\alpha b_\alpha}{2}\right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 + \rho\epsilon + \frac{1}{2}B^2 \text{ And}$$

$$\mathbf{S}_t = (\rho c^2 + \rho\epsilon + p + b^\alpha b_\alpha)\Gamma^2 \cdot v_j - \alpha b^0 b_j \rightarrow \rho \mathbf{v}, \text{ as well as } T_{\mu\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_\delta^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta} \right) \rightarrow 0 \text{ [10]}$$

The relativistic term hence recognizable to be then, are the source terms: $T_{\mu\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_\delta^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta} \right)$, coming due to the virtue of the nonlinear spacetime metric, which is now a variable, not a constant, like in the flat spacetime case. So condition for the validity of using the GRMHD equations instead of the non-relativistic equations, rest on the fact that the source terms have to be equivalent to the order of magnitudes of the stress-energy term. These can be easily found out by the Einstein Field Equations: $R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$ which relates the quantities of stress energy tensor and the Ricci curvature. From theory of general relativity, we know that as $R_{ij} := \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{\partial \Gamma_{ij}^a}{\partial x^a} - \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{\partial \Gamma_{ai}^a}{\partial x^j} + \sum_{a=1}^n \sum_{b=1}^n (\Gamma_{ab}^a \Gamma_{ij}^b - \Gamma_{ib}^a \Gamma_{aj}^b)$, where the Christoffel connections Γ_{ab}^c measure the deviation of direction of a parallel vector after one closed loop, which is the parameter for the curvature, where $\Gamma_{ab}^c := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{d=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial g_{bd}}{\partial x^a} + \frac{\partial g_{ad}}{\partial x^b} - \frac{\partial g_{ab}}{\partial x^d} \right) g^{cd}$. So by principle, $\left(\frac{\partial g^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_\delta^{\mu\alpha} g^{\delta\beta} \right) \rightarrow 0$, as the $R_{ij} \rightarrow 0$. To derive the condition, for which $R \gg 0$, for the GRMHD equations to be valid over the non-relativistic equations, one must take the reverse trace of the Einstein equations to write $R_{\mu\nu}$ in terms of the $T_{\mu\nu}$. The reverse trace form of the Einstein equations is

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} T g_{\mu\nu} \right) \text{ (98)}$$

Taking trace of both sides by multiplying both sides by $g^{\mu\nu}$, we get

$$R_\mu^\mu = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_\mu^\mu - \frac{1}{2} T g_\mu^\mu \right) = \frac{4\pi G}{c^4} T_\mu^\mu \text{ (99)}$$

For curvature scalar to be much greater than zero, $\frac{4\pi G}{c^4} T_\mu^\mu \gg 1$. Or trace of stress-energy must be much greater than $\frac{c^4}{4\pi G}$. Explicitly, by taking help of the energy momentum tensor, defined earlier, we can write the condition as

$$T_\mu^\mu = 3p^* - (\rho + \rho\epsilon + p + b^2)c^2 - b^2 \cong \frac{c^4}{4\pi G} \approx 3.027 \times 10^{43} \text{ Joules}/m^3 \text{ (100)}$$

Therefore, the net mass-energy content of the plasma has to be at least $3.027 \times 10^{43} \text{ Joules}/m^3$ for the GRMHD model to be applicable validly, otherwise the non-relativistic case is sufficient to describe their motion.

Now we can calculate the mechanical pressure, magnetic pressure, and the fluid density, by choosing a local inertial frame such the covariant derivative of the metric is zero. Note this is only locally true, the global conservation of momentum energy tensor will still have non-zero derivative of metric tensor, which governs the fluid equation. Having said that if we consider such a local inertial frame such that $\nabla_{\nu} g^{\alpha\beta} = 0$, the energy conservation equation in (94) will be

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} \tau_t}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} \tau_t \left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right) + p^* v^i - \frac{\alpha b^0 (\Gamma b^i - \alpha b^0 u^i)}{\Gamma}}{\partial x_i} \right) = 0$$

as, $T_{\mu\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_\mu} - \Gamma_0^{\mu\alpha} \alpha \right) \rightarrow 0$. Substituting the total energy density τ_t above, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{\gamma} \left(\left(\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p + \frac{B^2 + \alpha^2 (b^0)^2}{\Gamma^2} \right) \Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{B^2 + \alpha^2 (b^0)^2}{2\Gamma^2} \right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \right)}{\partial x_0} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\partial \sqrt{-g} \left(\left(\rho c^2 + \rho \epsilon + p + \frac{B^2 + \alpha^2 (b^0)^2}{\Gamma^2} \right) \Gamma^2 - \left(p + \frac{B^2 + \alpha^2 (b^0)^2}{2\Gamma^2} \right) - \alpha^2 (b^0)^2 \right) \left(v^i - \frac{\beta^u}{\alpha} \right) + p^* v^i - \frac{\alpha b^0 B^i}{\Gamma}}{\partial x_i} \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad [9]$$

Here, we have substituted the magnetic field, as measured in the lab frame by $b^i = \frac{B^i + \alpha b^0 u^i}{\Gamma}$, $b^0 = \frac{\Gamma B^i v_i}{\alpha}$ for the given metric, where we use the definition of the magnetic field b^i , (see chapter 3 page 29), comparing with the non-relativistic energy conservation equation,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon + \frac{1}{2} B^2 \right) + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho \epsilon + p + B^2 \right) \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B} \mathbf{B} \right] = 0$$

we shall get the relativistic mechanical pressure and the magnetic pressure term as

$$p_{rel} = p(\Gamma^2 - 1), \quad \frac{1}{2} B_{rel}^2 = B^2 + \frac{\alpha^2 (b^0)^2}{2\Gamma^2}$$

Substituting $b^0 = \frac{\Gamma B^i v_i}{\alpha}$ & $\Gamma^2 = \frac{1}{(1-v^2)}$ where $v^2 = \gamma_{ij} v^i v^j$, above we get $p_{rel} =$

$p \left(\frac{1}{(1-\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j)} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{2} B_{rel}^2 = B^2 + (B^i v_i)^2$. Simplifying the expression for p_{rel} we get the by expanding $\frac{1}{(1-\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j)} = 1 + \frac{\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j}{2} + \frac{3(\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j)^2}{8} + \dots$ up to 2nd order we get $p_{rel} = p \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j}{2} \right)$, and the magnetic pressure as $\frac{1}{2} B_{rel}^2 = B^2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{ij} v^i v^j}{2} \right)$.

Figure 11: Black Hole Accretion Disk [18]

These are the relativistic mechanical pressure and the magnetic pressure in the curved spacetime, where again as in the special relativistic case we see the mechanical pressure and the magnetic pressure as measured in the lab frame, become larger by power of the curvature tensor γ_{ij} and velocity. This is the case for spiralling plasma matter in an accretion disk around a black hole, where the increase in this stress generate high energy electromagnetic radiation, causing them to be excellent x-ray and gamma ray sources.

Chapter 5: Neutrino Magnetohydrodynamics.

5.1 Need for a Coupled Neutrino Fluid Model and Neutrino MHD

We, up until now, have discussed only the two fluid model of plasma, in various situations, in which plasma is considered to be composed of only ions and the electrons. But there are phenomena in space, involving plasma, in which the behaviour of plasma cannot be just explained by these two components alone. In the field of nuclear astrophysics, which studies the high energy phenomena in the space, many a times encounter scenarios, where motion of highly energetic fundamental particles are involved. Most of the times, these fundamental particles include not just electrons, but neutrinos as well. Perhaps, besides electron, neutrinos are the most common fermions, encountered in almost all astrophysical processes, which involve nuclear reactions.

Deep inside the matter, there is nucleus. In the nuclear length scale, there are two fundamental forces which dominate over the electromagnetic force, which are called the strong and the weak nuclear forces. Strong nuclear force is responsible for stability of the protons and neutrons, which make up all of the observable matter in the cosmos, and the weak nuclear force is known for being responsible for the nuclear decays, which triggers very powerful reactions. The stars are sometimes considered to be the fundamental unit of the cosmos, as they are the building blocks of larger and complex structures. In the core of the stars, the nuclei combine, under tremendous pressure to give birth to all the elements we observe in the cosmos, which happen due to the strong interaction. There is a huge quantity of energy gets released due to these processes, which gets exactly balanced by the gravitational potential energy of the stars. But this equilibrium does not last, as astrophysicists say that even after a lifetime of equilibrium, after a certain point, even the stars “die”; the stars’ internal nuclear fusion stops and the gravitational energy overwhelms nuclear energy, thereby starting a collapse. This collapse takes place in seconds, by a powerful nuclear explosion called Supernovae. Only the core of the star is left behind, which can be either a neutron star or a black hole depending upon the original mass of the star. During these process, in the outer layers, which are discarded and thrown into oblivion, higher mass elements are made by highly energetic scattering processes and decay, which happens due to the weak nuclear interaction between the neutrino and electrons, and other heavier unstable fermions.

Figure 12: Crab Nebula, one of the most famous supernova remnant [20]

Neutrinos are elusive particles weakly interacting with matter but playing a central role in several still unsolved astrophysical phenomena, including supernova explosions, the formation of structure in the Universe, and neutron star core cooling. significant amount of energy transfer between neutrino beams and plasma waves can take place over distances, thus suggesting that such a

mechanism could be crucial for the formation of an outgoing stalled shock in type II supernovae. Therefore, collective plasma effects tend to be more crucial than single particle processes, regarding the coupling to neutrinos. Such a coupling is described by the emergence of an effective neutrino charge in an ionized medium, producing kinetic and reactive instabilities as well as neutrino Landau damping of plasma waves. The heavy concentrations of neutrino taking place in these processes is the main need for us to take into consideration; thus, a new field of research is proposed, where one of the most popular approaches to space and laboratory plasmas, the magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) theory, is extended in order to incorporate neutrino dynamics. We shall, thus, develop an ideal plasma fluid model for a neutrino beam and an electron beam, coupled by the weak interaction, with immobilised ions. Our formulation will be completely non-relativistic. [11]

5.2 Fluid Neutrino Model

We start with the two-fluid equations for an electron-ion plasma coupled to a neutrino species, following the model we have theorized in Chapter 1. The mass and momentum transport equations for electrons (with mass m_e and charge $-e$) are respectively, collisions have been ignored as usual, considering only the linear motion:

$$\frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_e \mathbf{u}_e) = 0$$

$$m_e \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_e}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_e \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_e \right) = -\frac{\nabla P_e}{n_e} - e(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}) + \sqrt{2} G_F (\mathbf{E}_\nu + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}_\nu) \quad (101) [12]$$

while ions (with mass m_i and charge e) satisfy

$$\frac{\partial n_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_i \mathbf{u}_i) = 0$$

$$m_i \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}_i \right) = -\frac{\nabla P_i}{n_i} + e(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u}_i \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (102) [12]$$

Finally, the neutrino fluid satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial n_\nu}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_\nu \mathbf{u}_\nu) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{p}_\nu}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_\nu \cdot \nabla \mathbf{p}_\nu &= \sqrt{2} G_F (\mathbf{E}_e + \mathbf{u}_\nu \times \mathbf{B}_e) \end{aligned} \quad (103) [12]$$

When compared with the two fluid model, we note that only $\sqrt{2} G_F (\mathbf{E}_\nu + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}_\nu)$ & the term $\sqrt{2} G_F (\mathbf{E}_e + \mathbf{u}_\nu \times \mathbf{B}_e)$ have been added to show weak coupling between the electron and neutrino, giving rise to the neutrino force on the electron and the electron force on the neutrino, where two new effective fields, now arise in addition to electromagnetic fields, called the weak fields, which propagates the weak interaction. Here, $G_F = 1.45 \times 10^{-36} \text{ Jm}^3$ is the Fermi Constant. They are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_\nu &= -\nabla n_\nu - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (n_\nu \mathbf{u}_\nu), \\ \mathbf{B}_\nu &= \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla \times (n_\nu \mathbf{u}_\nu) \end{aligned} \quad (104) [12]$$

As well as the electromagnetic fields can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_e &= -\nabla n_e - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (n_e \mathbf{u}_e), \\ \mathbf{B}_e &= \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla \times (n_e \mathbf{u}_e), \end{aligned} \quad (105) [12]$$

We can simplify the momentum conservation equations above, by reducing the two fluid of ions and the electrons to one fluid model, like we did in Chapter 2, by defining the global mass, charge and current densities, and global fluid velocities

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= e(n_i - n_e), \quad \mathbf{J} = e(n_i \mathbf{u}_i - n_e \mathbf{u}_e) \\ \rho_m &= m_e n_e + m_i n_i, \quad \mathbf{U} = \frac{m_e n_e \mathbf{u}_e + m_i n_i \mathbf{u}_i}{m_e n_e + m_i n_i} \end{aligned} \quad (106) [12]$$

The equations (101) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m \mathbf{U}) &= 0 \\ \rho_m \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U} \right) &= -\nabla \cdot \Pi + \rho \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} + \left(\frac{\rho_m}{m_i} - \frac{\rho}{e} \right) \mathbf{F}_\nu \end{aligned} \quad (107) [12]$$

where, $\Pi = P\mathbf{I} + \frac{m_e m_i n_e n_i}{\rho_m} (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i)$. The second term $\frac{m_e m_i n_e n_i}{\rho_m} (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{u}_i)$ can be disregarded, where we assume a scalar pressure dominance over osmotic pressure. The neutrino force $\sqrt{2} G_F (\mathbf{E}_\nu + \mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}_\nu)$ can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{F}_\nu = \sqrt{2}G_F \left[\mathbf{E}_\nu + \left(\mathbf{U} - \frac{m_i \mathbf{U}}{\rho_m e} \right) \times \mathbf{B}_\nu \right]. \quad (108) [12]$$

We can now make very reasonable assumptions for the ideal MHD model, which can further simplify the one fluid model, which are follows: (a) formally infinite conductivity $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$, so that local charge unbalance can be disregarded, or $\rho \approx 0, n_e \approx n_i$; (b) we neglect the Hall term $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ in view of a high collision frequency in comparison to the gyro-frequency; (c) disregard relativistic corrections on MHD equations, since electrons and ions are assumed non-relativistic; adoption of the equation of state $\nabla P = V_S^2 \nabla \rho_m$, where V_S is the adiabatic speed of sound. The equations (103) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{E}_e = -\nabla n_e = -\nabla \rho_m / m_i, \mathbf{B}_e = 0 [12]$$

The neutrino momentum conservation equation (101) and one fluid equation for ions and electrons (105) can now be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{p}_\nu}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_\nu \cdot \nabla \mathbf{p}_\nu = -\frac{\sqrt{2}G_F}{m_i} \nabla \rho_m$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U} = -\frac{V_S^2 \nabla \rho_m}{\rho_m} + \frac{(\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0 \rho_m} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{m_i}. \quad (109) [12]$$

The Maxwell equations $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ can be rewritten as

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \left(\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{e} \right), \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial (\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{e})}{\partial t} \quad (110) [12]$$

Therefore, the equations for the Ideal Neutrino MHD model are

$$\frac{\partial n_\nu}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_\nu \mathbf{u}_\nu) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{p}_\nu}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_\nu \cdot \nabla \mathbf{p}_\nu = -\frac{\sqrt{2}G_F}{m_i} \nabla \rho_m$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U} = -\frac{V_S^2 \nabla \rho_m}{\rho_m} + \frac{(\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0 \rho_m} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{m_i}.$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0,$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times \left(\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{e} \right),$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial (\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{e})}{\partial t} [12]$$

where, all the symbols carry their usual meaning.

5.3 Validity of the Neutrino MHD Model and Some Results

We consider the neutrino interaction to be a perturbation over the general electromagnetic interactions in the plasma, which causes the neutrino force. As we have seen it is dependent on the neutrino number density. Taking in account of the perturbation we can series expand the neutrino number density n_ν & neutrino fluid velocity \mathbf{u}_ν to be expanded in a series, about its equilibrium value $n_{\nu 0}$ & $\mathbf{u}_{\nu 0}$

$$n_\nu = n_{\nu 0} + \varepsilon n_{\nu 1} + \varepsilon^2 n_{\nu 2} + \dots$$

$$\mathbf{u}_\nu = \mathbf{u}_{\nu 0} + \varepsilon \mathbf{u}_{\nu 1} + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{u}_{\nu 2} + \dots$$

Substituting this in the expression (106) for neutrino fields above and keeping only up to zeroth order term, we shall get

$$\mathbf{E}_\nu \approx \left(-n_{\nu 0} - \frac{n_{\nu 0} \mathbf{u}_{\nu 0}}{c^2} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_\nu \approx \frac{n_{\nu 0} \mathbf{u}_{\nu 0}}{c^2}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_\nu \approx \sqrt{2} G_F \left[\left(-n_{\nu 0} - \frac{n_{\nu 0} \mathbf{u}_{\nu 0}}{c^2} \right) + \left(\mathbf{u}_{\nu 0} - \frac{m_i \mathbf{j}}{\rho_m e} \right) \times \frac{n_{\nu 0} \mathbf{u}_{\nu 0}}{c^2} \right] \quad (111)$$

In the ideal non-relativistic case, it is clear that for the condition, for the neutrino force to be taken into account, $\mathbf{F}_\nu \gg 0$, so one need $G_F n_{\nu 0} \gg 0$. So, the $n_{\nu 0}$ should be at least of the order of $10^{35} m^{-3}$. If we have density of neutrino, less than this order, the equations for neutrino MHD will approach ideal MHD equations, as $\mathbf{F}_\nu \rightarrow 0$. This is the general number density of neutrino in typical neutron star parameters.

Now let us find the typical magnetic field strength in a neutron star. For doing so we consider a quasi static case, in which $\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U} \rightarrow 0$, $\mathbf{u}_\nu \rightarrow 0$, $\mathbf{F}_\nu \approx -\sqrt{2} G_F n_{\nu 0}$.

Considering a uniform density such that $\frac{V_S^2 \nabla \rho_m}{\rho_m} \rightarrow 0$, we can compare the Lorentz force and the neutrino force as $\frac{(\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0 \rho_m} \cong \frac{\mathbf{F}_\nu}{m_i}$. For $n_{\nu 0} \sim 10^{35} m^{-3}$, $\mathbf{F}_\nu \approx 10^{-1} \text{ N}$. Now as we did in the chapter 2 (see page no. 21), we define a characteristic length scale $L = \frac{m_i}{e(\mu_0 \rho_0)^{1/2}} \sim 10^{-5} m$.

The order magnitude of magnetic field obtained is about $\mathbf{B} \sim 10^{11} \text{ Tesla}$. These order of

Figure 13: Neutron Star merger MHD simulation [19]

magnetic field are usually generated during the merger of the neutron stars, during the process of which a huge flux of neutrino is generated.

Conclusion

We have presented in our work, a brief review of the formulation of four types of fluid models, namely quantum magnetohydrodynamics, special relativistic covariant magnetohydrodynamics, general relativistic magnetohydrodynamics, and the neutrino magnetohydrodynamics. In all four of the approaches, we have discussed their relevance in various astrophysical scenarios, the need of the development of the fluid models, under particular assumptions, apt for a particular energy scale, and length scale, derived the equations of motion, and then derived the typical values in the order of magnitude for some important physical quantities related to plasma. To be noted, that we have not looked for any solutions of the system of equations, as well as did not explore any of the wave dynamics of plasma, in this approach. We instead did an order of magnitude study and scaling analysis, for some important scenarios, frequently encountered in astrophysics, for study of objects, especially at a high energy scale such as neutron stars, relativistic jets, and black holes.

In the quantum mechanical fluid dynamic model, we found the typical order of number density of electrons/ions, a system should possess, in order for the model to be valid. We considered the case of a neutron star, where the density parameter typically satisfies the quantum MHD model, and found the order of magnitude of the magnetic field, as well as the mass density, and mechanical pressure, inside a neutron star. In the relativistic covariant formulation of plasma fluid dynamics, both in the general and the special case, a typical increase in both the mechanical pressure and the magnetic pressure was observed, when they were measured in the laboratory frame. This increase in the stress of the plasma is typical of the phenomena like relativistic jets, ejected by supermassive black hole, as well as, spiralling matter in the accretion disk of a black hole. In the neutrino MHD model, we calculated the typical order of magnitude of the neutrino number density for the model to be valid, as well as calculated the magnetic field, in the scenario of a neutron star merger.

MHD is thus a very useful tool in probing the cosmos, in a variety of length scale, whether it is predicting the motion of solar wind generated by the Solar Plasma, or the motion of degenerate matter deep in the heart of a neutron star. There is thus a very bright future for the MHD formulation in various astrophysical domain, in near future as well as beyond, as more observational data are gathered, in improvement of the formulations.

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